

The numeric map principle: A navigational-based hypothesis to explain the human skills to perform and understand basic arithmetic

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July 22, 2025

Abstract

One of the most challenging problems in neuroscience today is how numerical and arithmetic symbols acquire their meaning in the human brain. This problem is known as the symbol-grounding problem in numerical cognition (SGPNC). Different proposals for solving it have been made, but all of them have been disesteemed. This article presents a new hypothesis, the numeric map principle (NMP), regarding how the human brain is capable of giving meaning to arithmetic statements.

The NMP purports that the human brain uses its navigational system, which resides primarily in the hippocampal formation, to create a specific mental construct that would be indistinguishable from the mathematical structure that formalizes arithmetic. We name that construct “numeric map”. The research and results presented in this article are focused on how the human brain would use a numeric map to perform and understand arithmetic calculations with whole numbers.

To help the reader understand the background of the NMP, we summarize two main areas of research in neuroscience: numerical cognition and navigation. Next, we present the idea underlying the NMP and discuss and analyze it mathematically. Within the mathematical analysis, we provide a mathematical proof that shows that the navigational system can endow a semantic to the human brain to understand arithmetic with whole numbers. In addition, evidence is provided that supports the NMP, along with explanations of how it allows for explaining different phenomena that connect the central temporal lobe to mathematical skills.

If the NMP is correct, it will provide an important step forward for resolving the SGPNC and offer a new view on how the human brain works, as a result of connecting two major, previously disconnected areas of research: navigation and numerical cognition. Furthermore, if the NMP is confirmed, it will open new lines of research for making progress in solving the SGPNC.

1 Introduction

Connecting high-order cognitive processes and the electrical activity of neurons in the human brain is one of the greatest challenges facing neuroscience today. Among humans’ high-order cognitive abilities, mathematical skills are one of the most mysterious. Since ancient Greek times,

mathematics and mathematical skills have had mystical explanations (Anglin and Lambek, 1995). Even today, many mathematicians believe Platonism to be true (Gray, 2008), and some current scholars claim that mathematics has a superior position in the universe (Baron, 2024). One of the reasons human mathematical skills are so enigmatic is that they do not seem to have emerged from evolutionary pressures. Here, we are not discussing the capacity to estimate the cardinality or numerosity of one kind of element in an environment but the ability to perform arithmetic and other kinds of mathematics that involve mental objects without a physical counterpart and mental operations on those mental objects. While number estimation is clearly an advantageous trait for making decisions that increases fitness for individuals of species in specific niches, the capacity for understanding arithmetic does not seem to be a skill that animals require for surviving—otherwise it should exist in other species in their natural environments in addition to humans.

In contrast to these mystical ideas that many have held since ancient times, neuroscience has addressed the question of how the human brain generates mathematical skills. Initially, research on human mathematical skills was based on studying cognitive deficits resulting from brain damage (Kahn and Whitaker, 1991). Autopsies and later magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) allowed investigators to identify the damaged areas of the brains of individuals with deficits in mathematical skills. Based on the regions identified, different models were proposed regarding which areas are involved in mathematical abilities and which processes these regions carry out.

With the development of technologies that record brain activity and location, such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), investigations into mathematical skills experienced a revolution. These technologies allowed investigators to study mathematical skills in healthy subjects and test the proposed models and theories, such as the triple-code model (Dehaene, 1992; Dehaene and Cohen, 1995). The results of this line of research revealed that the parietal and prefrontal cortices in humans are involved in number and rule representation. However, neither the triple-code model nor any other model has provided a satisfactory answer regarding how the human brain performs and understands arithmetic.

A challenging problem in neuroscience today is the symbol-grounding problem in numerical cognition (SGPNC). The SGPNC poses the question of how numerical symbols and arithmetic operators acquire meaning in the human brain. The SGPNC is a specific case of the symbol-grounding problem (Harnad, 1990). It must be distinguished from the symbol-grounding problem in advanced mathematics, in which there are not numbers but only symbols and rules, as in infinitesimal calculus, differential equations, tensorial calculus, and metamathematics. Although substantial neuroscience research on human mathematical skills has led to identifying and describing the areas of the brain that display neuronal activity when humans use those skills, the discoveries made so far are not able to resolve the SGPNC. The difficulty of this problem arises from the fact that although one is able to create mental representations of numbers and manipulate them consciously as arithmetic dictates, one is also unable to determine how these representations are created and manipulated because they are subconscious processes.

Currently, the SGPNC is an open question, as the hypothesis proposed based on the approximate number system was proven to be false (Leibovich and Ansari, 2016; Reynvoet and Sasanguie, 2016). Thus, one current challenge is to elucidate the neuronal bases of the acquisition of symbolic mathematical knowledge (Merkley and Ansari, 2016).

In this article, we present the numeric map principle (NMP), which is a new hypothesis that we propose is the key to achieving an answer to the SGPNC. By connecting two research fields within neuroscience, the navigational system and human mathematical skills, this new hypothesis addresses how the human brain possesses a semantic that assigns meaning to arithmetic symbols and performs basic mathematical skills. We also discuss the NMP in detail and provide arguments that show that the navigational system has a fundamental role in explaining how the human brain

is able to perform arithmetic skills. The main idea behind the NMP is that the human brain uses the navigational system to understand and produce arithmetic. This principle proposes a new interpretation of the neuronal activity registered in the hippocampal formation when humans perform arithmetic operations, which until now has been interpreted as semantic memory activity in the research on mathematical skills. To the best of our knowledge, the NMP is a hypothesis that has never been considered in research on the navigational system, despite the navigational system's involvement in other cognitive processes (Lisman et al., 2017). Therefore, if the NMP is correct, it will be a significant step forward in understanding how the human brain functions because it explains how the two cognitive processes of navigation and numerical processing, which have been thoroughly investigated, are connected.

This paper addresses how the human brain would use a numeric map for performing arithmetic calculations with whole numbers and it is structured as follows: In Section 2, we provide a summary of the research on numerical processing conducted in the field of neuroscience until present day. Section 3 presents a summary of the main findings and discoveries related to the navigational system in the vertebrate brain for readers unfamiliar with this topic. Discussing the NMP and its role requires an understanding of the navigational system, and the information reviewed about the navigational system will help to understand the NMP and the subsequent discussions about it for readers who require an introduction to this field of neuroscience. Section 4 presents the NMP. First, we delve deeper into the SGPNC, and we describe the two criteria that should be met by a brain system that allows humans to create and understand arithmetic. Next, we present arguments showing that the navigational system fulfills those criteria. The following subsection is a mathematical proof that the human navigational system is able to allow humans to understand and produce arithmetic knowledge. The next subsection presents a precise formulation of the NMP, and the last subsection is dedicated to evidence that supports the NMP. In Section 5, we discuss the advantages of the NMP against previous interpretations and proposals, the NMP's impact on several topics, and open questions that emerge from the NMP. Finally, in Section 6, we present several conclusions and remarks.

2 The neural substrate of numerical processing

Mathematical skills are important for daily life in current society, and various disciplines have examined human mathematical skills for different reasons. For example, the main area of interest in neurology is how damaged brain structures in humans produce deficits in mathematical skills, and in psychology the focus lies in describing the cognitive processes related to human mathematical skills. Neuroanatomy research has tried to reveal which regions support mathematical abilities, whereas work in neuropsychology has attempted to uncover the relationship between brain activity and the cognitive processes of mathematical skills. Furthermore, pedagogy is interested in how humans acquire mathematical competencies and how they can be taught. Although comprehensively reviewing research from all these fields is beyond the goal of this paper, we present a short synthesis of some of the main discoveries about the neural substrate of mathematical skills to provide context for the hypothesis proposed in this paper.

Research in the field of human mathematical skills is closely linked to which noninvasive technology is available because most mathematical skills can only be studied in humans. We divide the research on human mathematical skills into two periods and review each period. We also highlight the prevailing model at this time, the triple code model, and discuss new discoveries

During the first period, the research on human mathematical skills was conceived as two independent areas: mathematical deficits and mathematical cognitive skills. The methods used to determine the regions associated with deficits included craniotomy, autopsies, clinical semiotic

patterns, and X-rays and computed tomography scans to localize the damage. The second period started with the use of new technologies that allowed registering neural activity while performing calculations in real time and unifying mathematical deficits and mathematical cognitive skills. The following is a brief summary of some of the most relevant findings and aspects of the research conducted about the neural substrate of the mathematical skills in each of those periods. This summary does not address the research carried out on numerical cognition in the discipline of psychology.

2.1 The first period: 1908 to 1984

In the 20th century, the objective of finding the calculation center in the human brain emerged as an important scientific question. Investigations into human mathematical skills started in the field of neurology in 1908, when Max Lewandowsky and Ernst Stadelmann published the first report of an individual unable to calculate simple sums due to a brain hemorrhage. They reported that the left occipital lobe was the area that contained the center of calculation (Lewandowsky and Stadelmann, 1908). Later, Salomon E. Henschen started a series of works that created a theoretical framework for calculation disorders. In 1919, he described dyscalculia, and in 1925, he introduced the term *acalculia* to define the impairment of mathematical abilities in individuals with brain damage.

One of the initial issues that emerged was which hemisphere was involved in mathematical calculations and what role each hemisphere played. Although some researchers claimed that the left hemisphere was the only one involved in mathematical calculations, others purported that both hemispheres were involved; however, opinions differed in the latter group regarding the role of the right hemisphere. For example, Henschen defended the existence of centers for calculation, which he claimed existed in the left hemisphere (Henschen, 1926). He also associated this idea with the fact that typically the left hemisphere is the dominant one. However, Henschen accepted that the right hemisphere was involved in calculations in a compensatory manner when the left hemisphere suffered a large lesion. On the other side of the argument, Goldstein believed that no proof existed that the minor hemisphere (typically the right) participated in calculation (Goldstein, 1948).

Another issue was which regions were involved in human mathematical skills. In 1918, Peritz argued that a “calculation center” existed in the left angular gyrus (Peritz, 1918). In addition, Henschen thought the angular gyrus was always implicated in calculation skills. However, Hans Berger claimed that the angular gyrus was not the only calculation center—he had found through a biopsy in a patient unable to perform division that a left hemisphere glioma reached into the posterior temporal and occipital lobes, but the angular gyrus and supramarginal gyrus were intact (Berger, 1926). Berger rejected the concept of a single calculation center corresponding to a specific brain site; he argued that mathematical skills involved different components working together. Furthermore, Goldstein argued that *acalculia* typically resulted from lesions in the parietal-occipital region and occasionally from the frontal lobes.

Questions about location and the role of the hemispheres were addressed in two independent investigations carried out by different authors but with similar conclusions that were presented in 1961. One by H. Hécaen (1961) and the other by Cohn (1961). Both investigations highlighted the fact that *acalculia* cases exhibited bilateral lesions primarily in parietal-occipital regions. Thus, the parietal hypothesis emerged, and this proposal was reinforced by Aleksandr R. Luria with his influential book *Higher Cortical Functions in Man* (Luria, 1966). He pointed out that the parieto-occipital areas, in addition to their role in linguistic operations, were also critical for arithmetic.

In addition to cortical research, investigators reported on patients who exhibited different

problems in number processing and calculation caused by noncortical damage. Specifically, in three patients with problems of acalculia, it was determined that the damage was non-cortical. In one case the damage was in the thalamus (Ojemann, 1974), in another case the damage was in the caudate nucleus (Whitaker et al., 1985), and in the last case, the damage was in the caudate nucleus, the putamen, and the anterior limb of the internal capsule (Corbett et al., 1986).

In 1930, Tobias Dantzig suggested the concept of number sense (Dantzig, 1930). He defined number sense as the faculty to know that the number of elements has changed after adding or deleting one element to the collection. He differentiated between the number sense and the mathematical skill of counting, and he considered that not only humans have number sense but also some animals would have it. However, Dantzig did not research the number sense, and the topic did not call the attention of the scientific community until many years later. Below we explain the concept of number sense.

During this first period, independent of the research on disturbances in the mathematical skills produced by brain damage, an important investigation focused on the physiological process leading to mathematical skills. The work of Jean Piaget made a drastic change to the framework by examining mathematical skills in children. Through his number conservation tests, Piaget showed that mathematical skills are developed and require acquisition (Piaget, 1952). Another research area was the mathematical skills already developed in adults. Robert S. Moyer and Thomas K. Landauer studied the process time required to judge numerical quantities (Moyer and Landauer, 1967). Their work prompted research on comparing quantities and the distance effect (Restle, 1970; Buckley and Gillman, 1974; Banks et al., 1976; Moyer and Bayer, 1976; Hinrichs et al., 1981). Measuring reaction times in mathematical operations, such as simple addition, was another relevant topic (Groen and Parkman, 1972). In that line of research, investigators measured the reaction times necessary to judge numerical quantities or mathematical operations, and they used the data to create models for mathematical operations. Another question that began to be explored was the mental representation that exists for numbers in the human brain (Shepard et al., 1975).

2.2 The second period: 1985 to present

The emergence of technologies that measure cerebral activity noninvasively started a new period in studying human mathematical skills. Previously, research involved identifying patients with brain damage and deriving conclusions about their problems with executing tasks based on the location of the damage. However, the advent of technologies such as radioactive positron emission tomography, fMRI, diffusion magnetic resonance imaging (dMRI), electroencephalography, and magnetoencephalography transformed investigations into human mathematical skills, allowing research on neuronal processes in healthy subjects. The key feature of the second period is that patients with brain trauma or damage remained an important source of data, but they were no longer the sole source. Here, we present a summary of the main lines of research carried out in this period.

In 1985, this second period began with the research of P.E. Roland and L. Friberg, who used intracarotid xenon-133 injections to measure cerebral blood flow in human subjects executing mathematical tasks (Roland and Friberg, 1985). In their experiments, they found activity in the left and right hemispheres, and in two specific areas: the prefrontal region and the inferior parietal region (near the angular gyrus). In 1994, Jordan Grafman, Denis Le Bihan, and other colleagues confirmed those results using fMRI (Appollonio et al., 1994). Those pioneering studies established how to investigate mathematical skills in a manner that remains ongoing today, and the spread of technologies that measure brain activity has led to an increase in research on the neural mechanisms underpinning human mathematical abilities.

Another important issue that marked the start of the second period also emerged in 1985, with a well-known article by Michael McCloskey, Alfonso Caramazza, and Annamaria Basili (McCloskey et al., 1985). Cognitive psychologists had been relying almost exclusively on data from healthy subjects to formulate and test cognitive theories, but in their article, McCloskey and his colleagues questioned the separation between studying normal mathematical skills and deficits resulting from brain damage. They claimed that dividing these issues was artificial, and as a result of studying patients whose mathematical skills had been affected by brain damage, they proposed the first cognitive model of calculation. They proposed that mathematical deficits emerge as a result of damage to one or more components in the cognitive system that support mathematical skills. By examining deficits in number comprehension, number production, and calculation, they formulated a model of the structure of the brain's normal number-processing/calculation system. This model, known as the abstract-modular theory, claims that three functionally distinct modules exist in the human brain that correspond to number comprehension, calculation, and production and that the brain has one single abstract code for representing numbers. One of the main hypotheses of the abstract-modular theory is the unitary hypothesis, which is the existence of one unique abstract and internal representation of numbers. McCloskey and his colleagues were able to show that two separate mechanisms exist, as their model claimed: one for storing mathematical facts and another for performing calculations (McCloskey et al., 1991a). That result was also observed in independent research (Weddell and Davidoff, 1991). Despite the initial success of the model, several researchers found discrepancies between the abstract-modular theory and what they observed in clinical studies (Campbell and Clark, 1988; Vaid and Frenck-Mestre, 1991; Cipolotti, 1995).

The approach proposed by McCloskey and his colleagues to formulate models caught the attention of the scientific community and other researchers began using it, and the realization spread that subjects with acquired cognitive deficits are a source of information for understanding normal cognitive processes. Along this line, in 1988, Jamie I. D. Campbell and James M. Clark presented the encoding complex theory (Campbell and Clark, 1988), which proposes that numerical skills are based on a variety of modality-specific codes. Campbell and Clark had found several problems with the abstract-modular theory and its claims. Specifically, they noted that the concept of abstract code is circular and that no known physiological mechanisms in the human brain are capable of realizing the idea of an abstract code (Clark and Campbell, 1991). They also provided evidence that internal mechanisms in different number tasks vary with the format of stimulus presentation (Clark and Campbell, 1991; Campbell and Clark, 1992). Thus, the encoding complex theory provided alternative ideas that avoided the problems found in the abstract-modular theory.

Eventually, the unitary hypothesis, one of the main cores of the abstract-modular theory, was found to be incorrect – in studying multiplication fact retrieval, it was observed that the spoken verbal form and written Arabic digit forms are dissociated (Deloche and Willmes, 2000). That fact determined that the abstract-modular theory had to be abandoned.

Using McCloskey's approach, Stanislas Dehaene proposed the triple code model (TCM) in 1992 (Dehaene, 1992). The TCM proposes that numerical information in the human brain can be manipulated using three codes: analogical code, verbal-auditory code, and Arabic visual code. The analogical code represents quantities and allows magnitude judgments. The verbal-auditory code represents numbers through sets of words, and the Arabic visual code represents the Arabic visual form. The TCM proposes that each one of the three types of codes may be translated to any one of the others without the mediation of an abstract code. Thus, the TCM claims that numbers are mentally manipulated in one of the three codes depending on the requested mental operation, and it predicts that three separate brain areas should be observed because each one processes one of the codes. Initially, the TCM was specified using single cases of patients with acalculia which their lesion was unambiguously localized (Dehaene and Cohen, 1995, 1997). One

interesting feature that distinguishes the TCM from the encoding complex theory is that it makes anatomical and functional claims. The TCM enunciated three different system, one for each code: a quantity system, a verbal system, and a visual system. The TCM outlines the following locations for the codes: the quantity system is in the inferior parietal areas, the verbal-auditory system is in the left perisylvian areas, and the visual system is in the ventral visual stream. Although some authors have identified problems with the TCM (Campbell, 1994; Deloche and Willmes, 2000), the TCM has been used as the starting point for many investigations into the validity of its claims due to its anatomical predictions.

The encoding complex theory was supported on different facts, but it also received criticism for not being defined in a precise manner (Deloche and Willmes, 2000). To address these concerns, Campbell and Lynette J. Epp presented a new model of basic numerical skills based on the ideas of the encoding complex theory and the results of experiments with Chinese-English bilinguals (Campbell and Epp, 2004). The encoding-complex model (ECM) combines the TCM with the encoding complex theory's approach to modeling number processing. The main feature of the ECM is that it expands the TCM by proposing that integrated encoding-retrieval processes exist within and between the representational systems and that the communication between the modular systems is iterative instead of only additive.

Given the large number of studies using newer technologies such as fMRI and dMRI to research human mathematical skills, several investigators have conducted meta-analyses to examine the TCM. In 2011, Marie Arsalidou and Margot J. Taylor performed a meta-analysis using a quantitative method called activation likelihood estimation to identify brain regions related to number and calculation tasks (Arsalidou and Taylor, 2011). They used 93 studies in their analysis, and they concluded that the TCM should be updated to add the following regions: right angular gyrus, insula, cerebellum, precentral gyri, and inferior, middle, superior frontal gyri, and dorsal cingulate gyri. They also proposed updating the model because it does not consider working memory. According to Arsalidou and Taylor, working memory is an important element in multistep problems, and the more difficult the mathematical task, the greater the need for working memory.

The TCM does not specify the neuroanatomical connections between the proposed brain areas for each code, so Klein et al. (2013a) began using probabilistic fiber tracking to examine connectivity within the frontoparietal network of numerical cognition. Their results showed that the processes of evaluating magnitude and retrieving facts are subserved by two largely separate networks. Furthermore, these findings have been supported by subsequent analysis of the connectivity, which identified the need for amending the TCM to include additional cortical areas and the connectivity between those areas (Klein et al., 2016). Delving deeper into determining the brain connectivity involved in numerical cognition, Moeller et al. (2015) carried out a meta-analysis of 27 studies. Their results showed that numerical cognition is supported not only by a frontoparietal network but also by connections between the cortex and basal ganglia as well as the thalamus. In their meta-analysis, they highlighted that the network that performs number processing also includes the hippocampus. The available data on brain connectivity suggest that the number of ways in which areas specified by the TCM might work together is greater than what was previously thought.

In the study of white matter, one important topic that emerged was the solution to a problem that existed between the TCM and certain clinical cases. It was known that some clinical cases contradicted the TCM because patients suffered mathematical deficits without brain damage in the locations the TCM specified for the corresponding code. To resolve that problem, Elise Klein, Korbinian Moeller, and Klaus Willmes proposed the disconnection hypothesis, which explained the cases without contradicting the TCM (Klein et al., 2013b). The disconnection hypothesis proposes that the disconnections of the dorsal and ventral fiber pathway systems also cause multiplication impairment. This hypothesis has been verified through various studies with stroke

patients (Mihulowicz et al., 2014; Smaczny et al., 2023).

Several investigations have addressed the existence of different locations in the human brain for each code predicted by the TCM. For example, the analog non-symbolic magnitude code has been localized in the intraparietal sulcus (Simon et al., 2002, 2004; Nieder, 2016), and the auditory verbal code has been localized in the inferior frontal gyrus, throughout the perisylvian language network (Schmithorst and Brown, 2004), and in the left angular gyrus (Dehaene et al., 2003). One of the most debated questions of the TCM is the existence of a specific visual area responsible for the visual Arabic code: the visual number form area (VNFA). In their experiments, Price and Ansari (2011) found activity associated with the VNFA in the left angular gyrus, and Shum et al. (2013) claimed that the VNFA is in the right inferior temporal gyrus. Abboud et al. (2015) studied the VNFA and the visual word form area (VWFA), with results showing that there is nothing visual about the VWFA because it can perform the function of determining the quantity of a symbol even if the sensory modality of the symbol is not visual. These results led to the renaming of the VNFA concept as the number form area (NFA). Grotheer et al. (2016) have stated that the NFA is in the left angular gyrus and performs its function early in the visual processing of numbers and letters. In their meta-analysis, Yeo et al. (2017) found that at least five candidate areas exist for the NFA, spanning the inferior and superior portions of the inferior temporal gyrus. To address the three numerical codes of the TCM within the same paradigm, Skagenholt et al. (2018) conducted an fMRI study in 2018. Their results indicated that the TCM correctly predicts the existence of dissociated neural substrates according to the different codes. Although these experiments did not allow for localizing the NFA, they identified a cluster within the right inferior temporal gyrus that exhibited preferential responses to Arabic numbers. The authors also observed that the TCM requires an update regarding the intervention of attentional processes during the performance of mathematical tasks. More recently, experiments have been conducted to study differences in how the human brain decodes numbers and words, and the results show that the dissociation between numbers and letters, when compared to false fonts, happens in a very early processing stage (Nara et al., 2023).

During this second period, fMRI and dMRI technologies have had a very important role in allowing investigators to study the development of mathematical skills. Some of the most outstanding work on this subject has been carried out by Vinod Menon and his collaborators. They have examined this question intensively, and several of their studies, which are listed below, have revealed that the hippocampus participates in the acquisition of mathematical skills. This discovery was unexpected because the participation of the hippocampus had been overlooked in most studies before the work of Menon and his collaborators.

In studying neurodevelopmental changes and mental arithmetic, Rivera et al. (2005) found that young subjects had a high level of activity in the hippocampus, specifically in the left hippocampus. The authors interpreted the activity to be part of a fact retrieval process for solving mathematical tasks. Rykhlevskaia et al. (2009) found prominent deficits in the hippocampus and entorhinal cortex in children with developmental dyscalculia compared with typically developing children. Cho et al. (2011) carried out experiments with better spatial precision than that of the previous investigations on children's strategy shift toward retrieval during early learning. The results showed definitive evidence of the differential engagement of the medial temporal lobe, where the hippocampus is located, between adults and children. The important discoveries by Menon and his collaborators regarding activity in the hippocampus were confirmed by De Smedt et al. (2011), who studied the effects of problem size in children's brain activity during arithmetic tasks; they found that the left hippocampus is particularly important in arithmetic because it was the only region of the default mode network that exhibited overlap in the effects of problem size and operation.

Once evidence confirmed the participation of the medial temporal lobe, Menon and his col-

laborators continued studying how it is related to mathematical skills. Cho et al. (2012) studied the hippocampal–prefrontal circuits to observe the neurodevelopmental changes associated with increased use of fact-retrieval strategies and to examine dynamic functional interactions. They found an important contribution of the hippocampal–prefrontal circuits to the early development of retrieval fluency in arithmetic problem solving. Supekar et al. (2013) showed that the prefrontal and medial temporal lobe areas, including the right hippocampus, left ventrolateral prefrontal cortex, and bilateral dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, are involved in the acquisition of math skills through tutoring. In addition, research on children with developmental dyscalculia has shown that activity in the hippocampus is related to better performance in accuracy and the number of missed trials (Rosenberg-Lee et al., 2015). The importance of the hippocampus in mathematical skills has also been confirmed in a study in which elementary school-age children participated in a training program to strengthen their mathematical skills (Chang et al., 2022). The researchers identified a hippocampal-parietal circuit that predicted individual differences in the children’s mathematical skills, and they also found that the circuit was strengthened by their training program.

The involvement of the hippocampus in mathematical skills has been interpreted to be a declarative memory activity required by mathematical skills, specifically because the processes that carry on the retrieval of facts (Menon and Chang, 2021; Kuhl et al., 2020; Peters and De Smedt, 2018; Menon, 2016; Moeller et al., 2015; Qin et al., 2014; De Smedt et al., 2011).

In 2016, Peters et al. (2016) carried out a study to explore how children’s brains employ the three codes described in the TCM. They found that the symbolic visual code and the symbolic verbal code use similar brain networks, but they also found clear differences between arithmetic with symbolic and non-symbolic codes. Their results were consistent with previous studies (Grabner et al., 2009; De Smedt et al., 2011; Menon, 2015) that showed that symbolic calculations rely on a bilateral frontal and superior parietal network, whereas non-symbolic calculations activate temporoparietal regions. In a meta-analysis of fMRI studies registering the brain activity of children performing numerical and calculation tasks, Arsalidou et al. (2018) found that mathematical performance in children is observed in the parietal and frontal areas determined by the TCM; however, the results also identified regions not previously recognized, such as the insula, claustrum, and cingulate gyrus. As an explanation for why those regions were active, the authors proposed that because children require intrinsic motivation to carry out difficult mental tasks, those kinds of tasks require controlling their attention and executing complex mental processes that cannot be automated. Recently, Skagenholt et al. (2021) has extended the research of Peters and his colleagues by examining the differences according to the TCM between children and adults performing numerical processes. They have observed that numerical discrimination abilities in middle-school-aged children are close to those in adults, so these results would serve as evidence that the development of mathematical circuits at 11 years old would be almost the same as those at adult-level developmental stages. Despite this similarity, they found a difference between children and adults in the discrimination of number words, as only the adults recruited left-lateralized perisylvian language areas.

Another important topic of this period was how mathematical skills emerged from an evolutionary point of view. This question is directly related to the issue about whether the basis of arithmetic is innate. Explaining how mathematical skills emerged evolutionarily requires finding that the systems or mechanisms supporting mathematical skills in humans and other animals are so similar that it points to the current systems being inherited from a common ancestor. Some experiments in the field of psychology in the 1990s seemed to indicate that the brains of humans (Wynn, 1992a) and animals (Gallistel and Gelman, 1992) had innate systems for representing numerosity and performing arithmetic operations. In parallel to the work being done in psychology, Stanislas Dehaene formulated Dantzig’s concept of number sense as a neuroscientific hypothesis about the brain (Dehaene, 1997). The number sense hypothesis proposes that numerosity is a perceptual

category provided by hard-wired sensory brain processes, and therefore, an animal can possess numerical skills without the need to learn what numerosity refers to. Dehaene also proposed that number sense is generated by an innate system, which he named the approximate number system (ANS).

Extensive research has been conducted to discover whether animals (including humans) have number sense. In 2002, two independent groups researching primates found neurons that were tuned to a specific number of items shown to them (Nieder et al., 2002; Sawamura et al., 2002). Nieder et al. (2002) found neurons tuned to the number of visual items in the prefrontal cortex, and Sawamura et al. (2002) found neurons in the parietal cortex with the same kind of response. Nieder and Merten (2007) trained monkeys to discriminate numerosities from 1 to 30 and found neurons tuned to a specific numerosity in the range from 1 to 30 in the prefrontal cortex. However, these discoveries could not sufficiently prove the existence of number sense because the primates had received training to execute the experiments, and the number sense hypothesis claims that an innate system exists that allows determining the numerosity of items in an environment (Roitman et al., 2012). In 2013, Viswanathan and Nieder (2013) was able to record neurons in the ventral intraparietal sulcus and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex of monkeys without any training in numerical issues, and they identified neurons in both areas tuned to the number of visual items. They also observed that numerical information is conveyed from the parietal to the frontal lobe. Furthermore, different investigations have shown that different animals are able to discriminate between different nonsymbolic numerosities (Cantlon and Brannon, 2006; Agrillo et al., 2011), and the skill has been observed in human infants (Libertus and Brannon, 2009).

Initially, Dehaene purported that number sense relies on one single system, the ANS. However, various experiments provided evidence of two different estimation systems (Feigenson et al., 2002; Xu, 2003; Lipton and Spelke, 2004), which led to formulating the notion of two systems of numerical representations (Feigenson et al., 2004). The second system has been denominated the object tracking system (OTS)(Xu, 2003), or parallel individuation system (Piazza, 2010). In 2008, Susannah K. Revkin performed an experiment that refuted the single-estimation system hypothesis (Revkin et al., 2008), and it has recently been shown that two different systems exist for representing small and large numbers (Kutter et al., 2023).

Despite the investigations previously mentioned, the idea of an ANS and the existence of number sense have been questioned. Some authors have questioned the existence of a independent system that specifically calculates the numerosity (Leibovich et al., 2017), and they claim that the results of the experiments about numerosity could be explained considering only a sense of magnitude. Independent of whether numerosity is an independent perceptual category or not, additional research is currently being conducted to better understand the ANS (Pickering et al., 2023), its nature and how it works (Kuzmina et al., 2023).

Alongside the question of how mathematical abilities have evolutionarily emerged, the question of how numerical symbols acquire meaning in the human brain has also been posed. This question is called the symbol-grounding problem in numerical cognition (SGPNC) because it is a specific case of the symbol-grounding problem (Harnad, 1990). The SGPNC must be distinguished from the symbol-grounding problem in advanced mathematics, in which there are not numbers but only symbols and rules, as in infinitesimal calculus, differential equations, and tensorial calculus. Dehaene proposed that the answer to the SGPNC is number sense (Dehaene, 1997), and that hypothesis was the mainstream viewpoint for almost two decades (Izard and Dehaene, 2008; Piazza, 2010; Wagner and Johnson, 2011; Feigenson et al., 2013; Bugden et al., 2016). Regarding the fact that number sense consists of two systems, the OTS and ANS, the question of which one is involved in providing a meaning to numerical symbols emerged. Given that experimental research did not provide evidence that the OTS played a role in the SGPNC, the hypothesis that the ANS was key

to the SGPNC seemed the most feasible. Furthermore, regarding how numerical symbols acquire meaning through the ANS, two different mechanisms were proposed to explain the process (Piazza, 2010). One such mechanism was associative mapping, and the other was structure mapping (Carey, 2009; Gentner, 2010). The associative mapping hypothesis claims that symbolic numbers achieve their meaning through a mapping of numeric symbols to the analog code generated by the ANS, whereas the structure mapping hypothesis states that number symbols and the analog code are mapped onto each other. While the study of those mechanisms has shed light on how numerical estimations are generated (Sullivan and Barner, 2013), it has also become clear that neither of the two proposals that involves the ANS is the answer to the SGPNC.

The ANS mapping account started to be questioned as a solution to the SGPNC by Negen and Sarnecka (2015), who presented problems with previous experiments and claimed that the results showed a correlation between young children’s ANS acuity and their formal mathematical knowledge. They also discussed experiments showing that the correlation in normally developing children disappears. Next, Leibovich and Ansari (2016) harshly criticized the ANS mapping account. They highlighted that the associations between the ANS and symbolic math were inconsistent because the results of different experiments contradicted the predictions that are a consequence of the ANS mapping account. Reynvoet and Sasanguie (2016) also joined in the criticism. They evaluated the main four arguments that supported the ANS mapping account and concluded that the arguments were questionable; they proposed studying a symbol-symbol association account as an alternative to answer the SGPNC. Furthermore, Carey and colleagues’ experiments have shown that the ANS does not provide the numerical content of even small numerals (Carey et al., 2017), and they have argued against the ANS mapping account on the basis that the approximate number representations fail to provide the content required of integer concepts (Carey and Barner, 2019). Other arguments that have emerged against the ANS mapping account is that the conclusions drawn from certain experiments stating that children would use the ANS to provide meaning to early number words are incorrect (Wagner et al., 2019). More recently, Wilkey and Ansari (2020) have conducted a review showing the weaknesses of the ANS mapping account. While it is clear that the ANS mapping account cannot explain the SGPNC, we also lack a new proposal to answer the SGPNC. We will go into the SGPNC in more detail below in Section 4.

2.3 New technologies and discoveries

The investigations in humans during the second period used technologies that register brain areas, such as fMRI, dMRI, electroencephalography, and magnetoencephalography. Given that these technologies can only detect activity when a large number of neurons fire synchronously, drawing conclusions about a deeper level of understanding of human mathematical skills requires the capacity to study individual neuronal activity. This method has been done in monkeys, but monkeys do not have the same level of mathematical skills that humans have, and for ethical reasons, the type of research applied in monkeys cannot be done in humans. However, the inability to obtain data from individual neurons has changed over the last few years due to the implantation of intracranial electrodes in patients with epilepsy. Intracranial electrodes allow single neurons to be registered, and the precision of intracranial electrodes has revealed new data about mathematical skills. The first unforeseen discovery was the existence of neurons tuned to numerical values in the medial temporal lobe (Kutter et al., 2018). A second unexpected finding was the existence of cells tuned to arithmetical rules in the medial temporal lobe (Kutter et al., 2022).

Another technology that allows registering individual neuronal activity is planar multichannel microelectrode arrays (MEAs) (Eisenkolb et al., 2023). Using MEAs, researchers examined neurons in the parietal cortex of humans performing numeric tasks. Data from this work has uncovered

neurons tuned to a specific numerosity, showing the same kind of code observed in monkeys in the experiments researching number sense.

3 The skill of navigation and the hippocampal and parahippocampal formation

In the 1930s and 1940s, Edward Tolman offered a view on animal learning that was different from the one that dominated psychology at the time. While the majority position was behaviorism, he defended the cognitive approach as being necessary to explain some behaviors. In 1948, after he and his collaborators conducted experiments to examine rats moving through a spatial layout of a maze, Tolman introduced the concept of cognitive maps to explain the rats' behavior (Tolman, 1948). A cognitive map is a type of mental representation that contains spatial information about an environment and the objects that exist within it. It allows for planning a route with the goal of choosing or avoiding locations. With the discovery of place cells, the concept of cognitive maps moved from psychology to neuroscience. John O'Keefe and his student Jonathan Dostrovsky discovered place cells in the hippocampus (O'Keefe and Dostrovsky, 1971), and in their well-known book, O'Keefe and Lynn Nadel proposed that place cells are part of the neural substrate that allow the brain to possess a cognitive map (O'Keefe and Nadel, 1978).

Currently, the hippocampal formation is one of the regions most studied in the mammalian brain, and the idea of determining whether it actually contains the circuits that implement a system capable of generating a cognitive map has been one of the main drivers of research in that brain region. Research on the hippocampal and parahippocampal formation has resulted in an important body of knowledge on how the brain generates a spatial representation and how it uses it to navigate, although gaps still remain regarding how the brain carries out that function completely (Morris and Derdikman, 2023).

Here, we summarize the main points regarding the navigational system in the vertebrate brain relevant to the hypothesis presented in this article. Specifically, we focus on the mechanism that supports the allocentric spatial representation of an environment. Readers interested in details beyond those provided in this article can read general reviews already written on the topic (Moser et al., 2017; Rolls, 2023) or reviews about specific issues related to the navigational system, such as place cells (Cobar et al., 2017), head direction (Hulse and Jayaraman, 2020), microcircuits of the medial entorhinal cortex (Tukker et al., 2022), vector coding (Bicanski and Burgess, 2020), and replay (Pfeiffer, 2020).

3.1 Place cells and remapping

The navigational system of the mammal (and vertebrate) brain began to be unveiled when O'Keefe and Dostrovsky (1971) discovered that when a rat was in a certain position in an environment, a specific cell in its hippocampus fired. Those kinds of cells are called place cells because each one denotes a specific position in an environment, and they have been registered in CA1, CA3 (Lee et al., 2004), and the entorhinal cortex (Leutgeb et al., 2007). The spatial receptive fields of place cells do not have a sensory origin, but they are higher-order integrators of sensory data. Figure 1 shows the positions of an environment where different place-cells fire.

A feature observed in various experiments is that place cells maintain their location specificity after removing many of the landmarks that were originally located in the environment (Muller and Kubie, 1987; O'Keefe and Speakman, 1987). The entire environment is represented in the activity of place cells, and each place cell represents a different location because a different place cell is firing at each location, and this representation of locations in the environment remains in

3.4 Conjunctive grid x head-direction cells

After grid cells were found, a new kind of cell was observed that integrates information from grid and head direction cells. These cells have been named conjunctive grid x head-direction cells (Sargolini et al., 2006).

3.5 Border cells and vector cells

The next important discoveries on the navigational system were related to cells that provide details about the environment. The first of these discoveries was border cells (Solstad et al., 2008). When an animal is located near the geometric borders of the local environment, a border cell is fired. These cells exist in layers II and III of the MEC and in the hippocampus and subiculum. Another finding involved three new kinds of cells that provide different details about the environment: boundary vector cells (Lever et al., 2009), landmark vector cells (Deshmukh and Knierim, 2013), and object vector cells (Høydal et al., 2019). It is interesting to note that theoretical models of the navigational system had predicted that boundary vector cells exist (O'Keefe and Burgess, 1996). These three types of vectorial cells reference locations different from the animal's current position where a feature or object exists at a location in the environment's structure.

3.6 The environment's geometric center

Recently, center-bearing and center-distance cells have been identified (Patrick A. LaChance, 2019). Center-bearing cells encode the egocentric bearing of the center of the arena, and center distance cells are tuned to express the absolute distance from the center of the arena. Both center-bearing and center-distance cells have enough information to represent the center of the environment, and these two types of cells have been found in the rat's postrhinal cortex (the rodent homolog of the human parahippocampal cortex). Furthermore, a type of head direction cell has been found in the postrhinal cortex. The information from center-bearing and center-distance cells combined with that from head direction cells could encode the allocentric location of the animal.

3.7 Corner cells

The last type of cell we are going to mention is corner cells. Changes in the environment can alter the grid cell and place cell firing patterns that represent spatial changes in the environment. However, neither of those kinds of cells are encoding geometric properties. In investigating which neural substrate encodes the geometric properties of an environment, a new kind of cells, named corner cells, have just been discovered (Sun et al., 2024). This new kind of cell represents concavity and convexity features of the environment. The research has located corner cells in the subiculum, and their firing encodes the corner angle, wall height, and distance to walls. The investigation has also shown that corner coding in the subiculum is primarily allocentric.

3.8 Replay and goal-oriented representations

In addition to discoveries about how the brain represents spatial locations in an environment, it has been found that animals carry out a process in the place cells of the hippocampus that encodes the paths an animal has followed in an environment (Pfeiffer, 2020). The first report of this process, which is called replay, occurred in 1989 (Pavlides and Winson, 1989), and in 1994, it was shown that the same place cells that fire together for spatial exploration also fire during sleep (Wilson and McNaughton, 1994). It was subsequently found that activity patterns during sleep follow the same order in which the cells fire during spatial exploration (Skaggs and McNaughton,

1996). It has also been shown that the sequences reactivated for sleep are a temporally compressed version of the sequences generated during spatial exploration (Nádasy et al., 1999) and that the sequences generated during sleep are associated with the explored environment (Hirase et al., 2001). Another important finding about the replay process is that it not only occurs during sleep but also during the awake state (Kudrimoti et al., 1999; Jackson et al., 2006). Research on the awake replay process has revealed an important finding, reverse replay (Foster and Wilson, 2007), which is the reactivation of place cells in the temporal order opposite to the sequence that occurs while the animal navigates through the environment. Thus, it is known that two kinds of replay exist for the awake state—forward and reverse (Davidson et al., 2009)—and that the sequences of the place cells activated during replay hold the topology of the environment (Wu and Foster, 2014).

The finding that the replay process represents paths through the environment has led to research on the role of replay in planning paths toward a future goal. Recently, it has been shown that replay represents the simulation of a path planned toward a future goal (Widloski and Foster, 2022), and this discovery has opened many questions about how the brain plans a trajectory (McNaughton and Saxena, 2022; Epsztein, 2022). Also, recently, it has been addressed through experiments in virtual environments whether a rat can use volitionally the maps represented in its hippocampus (Lai et al., 2023). Using two brain-machine interface tasks, the results of the experiments have shown that rats can control their hippocampus activity to navigate and direct objects to arbitrary goal locations.

3.9 Extrahippocampal contribution to spatial navigation

As we have shown, although place cells were initially discovered in the hippocampus, research has found that the navigational system involves other areas. We have mentioned that some discoveries have been made in the parahippocampal and entorhinal cortex, but the retrosplenial complex, dorsal striatum, and posterior parietal cortex also play a role in navigation (Baumann and Mattingley, 2021). Research has indicated that the retrosplenial cortex is involved in transforming egocentric spatial information to allocentric coordinates (Alexander et al., 2023). Support for this view can be found in the existence of egocentric boundary cells in the retrosplenial cortex (Alexander et al., 2020), which was predicted by models that propose that the retrosplenial cortex is involved in transforming the egocentric coordinates of boundaries to allocentric coordinates (Bicanski and Burgess, 2018). From a general perspective, the retrosplenial complex and parahippocampal cortex are thought to have complementary functions for spatial navigation (Epstein, 2008). The parahippocampal cortex’s function would be encoding a representation of the local scene to be stored and recognized, whereas the retrosplenial complex’s function would be orienting oneself within the broader spatial environment that requires egocentric coordinates. Recent research has shown that single neurons of the postrhinal and retrosplenial cortices represent egocentric information, but each one is focused on different kinds of egocentric information (LaChance and Hasselmo, 2024). Postrhinal egocentric bearing cells respond to local features, and retrosplenial egocentric bearing cells represent global features of the environment. Studies have shown that both regions have a strong connectivity with the hippocampal formation (Wyass and Van Groen, 1992; Burwell et al., 1995; Naber et al., 2001; Agster and Burwell, 2013), and those results allow a better understanding of how the allocentric representation of the environment is generated from egocentric information.

The dorsal striatum is known to be relevant for spatial navigation, according to studies in which rats with lesions in this location showed serious problems in navigation (Potegal, 1969). The current view about the function of the dorsal striatum is linked to stimulus response learning relative to individual landmarks (Gahnstrom and Spiers, 2020). One relevant detail about the posterior parietal cortex (PPC) is that it is interconnected to the retrosplenial cortex, which is interconnected

with the hippocampus. It has also been discovered that cells specifically tuned for directions to visual cues exist in the PPC (Snyder et al., 1998), which are named egocentric cue direction cells. The PPC’s anatomical location and these discoveries have led scientists to consider that the PPC is involved in encoding the representation of self-body motion through space (Whitlock et al., 2008). Only a few studies have addressed the role of PPC in navigation, but the results indicate that PPC codes self-motion and egocentric target positions (Alexander et al., 2022) (Lyamzin and Benucci, 2019)(Whitlock et al., 2012).

4 The symbol-grounding problem in numerical cognition and the numeric map principle

We currently have knowledge about human mathematical skills in three domains: cognitive processes, neural systems, and anatomical locations. Despite this information, we are far from a complete understanding of how the human brain possesses mathematical skills. Two of the main unresolved issues are the SGPNC and how the human brain carries out arithmetic operations. These two issues are closely related because if we know how the human brain endows a semantic to symbols, we can understand how the brain carries out arithmetic operations and vice versa. In this section, we present the numeric map principle (NMP), a new hypothesis about how the human brain is able to perform these two topics. Before presenting the NMP, we delve deeper into the research that has been conducted to date on these two issues.

As mentioned in Section ??, the SGPNC is one of the most important questions that must be answered to advance our understanding of how the human brain carries out high-level cognitive skills. The symbol-grounding problem asks how the meaning of symbols is grounded in something other than just more meaningless symbols (Harnad, 1990). The SGPNC asks how a brain gives meaning to numerals and operator symbols. We know that the brain can learn mathematical facts, but learning a fact and merely repeating it verbally or writing it down does not mean that the person understands its meaning. For example, one could write down a sequence of mathematical symbols $30 \odot 40 = 38$, and that sequence could be learned and retrieved as a mathematical fact. However, that mathematical expression does not have any meaning because a meaning for the symbol \odot does not exist. Therefore, it is important to distinguish between retrieving a mathematical fact and understanding a mathematical fact. If we substitute the operator \odot with $+$, we have a meaning for the mathematical expression $30 + 40 = 38$, and we would say that $30 + 40 = 38$ is false because its meaning contradicts the meaning of the symbols that compose the expression. When children receive mathematics education, they learn summation tables, subtraction facts, and multiplication tables; however, they learn multiplication mainly as arithmetical facts because we use algorithms for multiplying numbers, but they achieve a deep understanding of summation and subtraction even though summation tables and subtraction facts are also learned. Such an understanding is not possible without acquiring meaning for numbers and operations symbols.

Therefore, understanding mathematics does not consist of simply answering mathematical questions by retrieving mathematical facts because retrieving a mathematical fact is merely repeating a sequence of symbols that has been stored, and understanding a mathematical fact requires knowing why one specific mathematical fact is the answer to a mathematical question. For example, if one must answer: What is the result of $2 + 3$? they can retrieve the fact that $2+3=5$ and also explain why it is true and why $2 + 3 = 4$ is false. Thus, understanding a fact requires that one can determine whether a mathematical statement is true or false, and determining the truth value is related to knowing the meaning of each symbol. Knowing the meaning of each symbol allows determining whether the meaning of the expression contradicts the meaning of the symbols

that compose the expression and generating new expressions not learned before. In this paper, we specifically address the question of how the adult human brain is able to understand the symbols of basic arithmetic expressions with whole numbers.

The scientific community's stance on how the human brain achieves dominance in mathematical knowledge has been alternating between constructivism and innatism. In the field of psychology, after Piaget's work (Piaget, 1952), the mainstream point of view for several decades was constructivism, which states that children acquire mathematical knowledge through their actions and interactions with the physical world. However, in the 1980s, studies on the mathematical skills of human infants and newborns started to be performed, and the results showed that they are able to discriminate small numerosities (Starkey and Cooper, 1980; Strauss and Curtis, 1981; Treiber and Wilcox, 1984). In 1992, Karen Wynn presented the results of experiments that showed that human infants only a few months old were able to calculate simple arithmetic operations with small numbers (Wynn, 1992a). Wynn considered the innate skills to be the basis for the development of arithmetic knowledge (Wynn, 1992b). Also, on the basis of psychological experiments they had carried out, Charles R. Gallistel and Rochel Gelman proposed that human mathematical skills rely on an innate system for representing a numerosity that is shared with other animals (Gallistel and Gelman, 1992). In support of this idea, Whalen et al. (1999) presented evidence from psychological experiments that an innate system exists that is shared by humans and other animals.

In the field of neuroscience, as mentioned in Subsection 2.2, Dehaene proposed his hypothesis regarding the existence of number sense (Dehaene, 1997). Interestingly, Dehaene's number sense hypothesis relied heavily on the results of psychological experiments on human infants, newborns, and animals that demonstrated the existence of innate mathematical abilities. The search for the neural mechanisms of number sense led to the discovery of two innate systems, the OTS and ANS, that are responsible for the innate mathematical skills obtained in these experiments with animals and human infants and neurons tuned to specific numerosities previously mentioned in Section 2.2.

Although psychology and neuroscience seemed to be close to a solution to the SGPNC because the research showed that human mathematical knowledge emerged due to innate mechanisms in the human brain, additional experiments indicated that the core of mathematical skills is more elusive than previously thought. However, psychological experiments with human infants in the 2000s showed that those innate skills do not involve understanding arithmetic operations (Vilette, 2002; Cohen and Marks, 2002). In neuroscience, the OTS was discarded as the mechanism in which the meaning of mathematical symbols was grounded (Piazza, 2010), and the research shifted to focus solely on the ANS. The ANS hypothesis claims that numerical symbols (e.g., digits or number words) are mapped onto a nonverbal and analog representation of numbers. The ANS hypothesis is directly related to the TCM because it proposes that the quantity system that is stated in the TCM would be the element that grounds the numeric symbols. However, research has shown that the ANS is not able of endowing a semantic to pure numerical symbols (numbers, arithmetic operations, etc.) and generating arithmetic knowledge. The systems that support number sense are able to explain the innate capacity to estimate a cardinality of a list or set of entities, but they are not able to explain how the human brain bestows a semantic to numbers and arithmetic operations.

We explained in Section ?? that different authors have highlighted that the ANS is not an answer to the SGPNC (Lyons and Ansari, 2015; Leibovich and Ansari, 2016; Reynvoet and Sasanguie, 2016; Carey et al., 2017; Carey and Barner, 2019; Wilkey and Ansari, 2020). In addition, a recent investigation has shown that two ANS representations cannot be multiplied (Pickering et al., 2023). The results and issues discussed above provide strong evidence for concluding that ANS representations are not the ground for numerals and that the ANS cannot be the core of how the human brain endows a semantic to arithmetic symbols. Although research has shown that innate abilities exist, it also seems to indicate that these innate abilities are not the ones that have allowed

us to generate and understand arithmetic. Answering how a symbol acquires its numerical meaning involves more than achieving a system with the ability to possess numerosity; a number is not a number in itself because it involves the relationship of that number with all the other numbers and operations. Thus, the SGPNC is currently an open problem.

Another important issue that must be resolved to understand how the human brain masters mathematical knowledge is how it is able to perform arithmetic calculations. Among the models that attempt to explain how the human brain carries out number processing, the TCM is considered the most successful theory for its description of how the human brain possesses its mathematical skills. As mentioned in Subsection 2.2, the TCM proposes the existence of three codes to represent numbers and two routes through which arithmetic happens (Dehaene and Cohen, 1997). On the one hand there is a direct route, when solutions are retrieved as facts from semantic memory, mainly during multiplication. This route has been linked to the verbal code located in the left temporo-parietal language-related areas. The indirect route, on the other hand, is used when the solution to a problem cannot be immediately retrieved from memory, and a procedural manipulation, potentially relying on the magnitude code, is needed (Peters et al., 2016). The TCM proposes that the quantity system, which represents numbers in the magnitude code, provides a semantic representation of the size and distance relations between numbers in the parietal cortex (Dehaene, 2001; Hubbard et al., 2005). Specifically, the model proposes that the quantity system is located in an area of the intraparietal sulcus, which might be the primary region to process numerical information (Dehaene et al., 2003). Dehaene and his colleagues named that area the horizontal part of the intraparietal sulcus (hIPS). The TCM proposes that the hIPS is the key region for the mental manipulation of numerical quantities because it seems to host a format-independent representation of numerical quantity. Although the results from an initial imaging study supported that idea (Piazza et al., 2007), other studies have questioned the existence of a format-independent numerical representation in the IPS because it has been shown that symbolic and nonsymbolic numbers may be represented more distinctly than was previously assumed (Bulthé et al., 2015, 2014). Beyond that dispute, the TCM lacks an interpretation of how neuronal activity in the hIPS can perform arithmetic operations, and unlike other claims that the TCM makes that allows making testable predictions, the statement that the hIPS deals with numerical manipulation is an idea that does not resolve how the human brain carries out arithmetic operations. Therefore, neuroscience has not yet been able to unveil the neural circuits that carry out arithmetic operations such as addition, subtraction, and multiplication and even less is known about how neural circuits are able to perform these processes.

After the previous review on the current state of open questions regarding the SGPNC and how the human brain can perform arithmetic operations, one can recognize that these two questions are challenging and need to be resolved in order to advance our understanding of how the human brain works. For that reason, the target of the research presented in this paper is to achieve an explanation of how the human brain understands and carries out arithmetic operations with whole numbers. Before presenting the proposed solution, we introduce three conditions that can be used to guide the search for a solution to the aforementioned issues and discard options that have been deduced for the research presented here. Also, the fact that these conditions are met by a proposal provides an initial argument that supports the proposal as a solution to the issues that are the focused on this research. Given that the hypothesis that innate mechanisms in the brain can explain human arithmetic skills resulted in a dead end, one must return to the idea that arithmetical knowledge is acquired from interactions with the environment. However, acquiring arithmetic knowledge cannot be explained merely by the human brain being a tabula rasa because it cannot not clarify how the human brain generates this knowledge; although many people are taught arithmetic, some also develop it. Thus, the human brain must possess a data structure that

allows not only learning that knowledge but also creating it, which generates a key question for addressing the SGPNC and how the human brain can perform arithmetic operations: what kind of data structure does the human brain use to learn, manipulate, and generate arithmetic knowledge? Answering this question from a neuroscientific point of view requires resolving the two following issues:

- Identifying the neural system that endows a semantic to the arithmetic knowledge and manipulates it.
- Providing a high cognitive level interpretation of the neural activity of the neural system to explain how human arithmetic skills emerge.

The importance of determining the neural system is obvious, but the reader might wonder why interpreting neural activity is important. To understand how mathematical human skills emerge from neuronal activity, it is not sufficient to know the neuronal system—we require an interpretation of the neural activity at a high cognitive level so that we can understand what process the neuronal system carries out.

But how can one identify the neuronal system responsible for human arithmetic skills? According to the features observed in this process, some specific conditions can be established that must either recognize whether a neural system is potentially capable of enabling the generation and understanding of arithmetic or that must rule it out. These conditions are the following:

- **C1:** The neural system activity must allow creating, storing, and manipulating mental representations.
- **C2:** The neural system must not be driven by sensory input and allow volitional mental activity.
- **C3:** The neural system activity must produce manipulations of the mental representations that match with the true arithmetic statements.

Condition **C1** is based on the fact that while children receive mathematical education, a process of internalizing arithmetic concepts occurs that allows them to perform mental arithmetic, and we also know that adults can receive training to internalize arithmetic concepts.

Condition **C2** is based on the fact that adult humans can carry out mental arithmetic without any kind of sensory input since a human being is able to represent numbers mentally and execute mental arithmetic due to volitional activity.

Condition **C3** determines whether a system that fulfils **C1** and **C2** is potentially a system that can be used by the human brain to generate and understand arithmetic knowledge, since verifying that a match exists between the manipulations that can be done by the neuronal system and the true arithmetic statements means that the system replicates the arithmetic structure, which in turn allows grounding arithmetic symbols.

The proposal stated in this paper is that the human brain’s neural system that provides meaning to arithmetic expressions is the navigational system located mainly in the hippocampal formation. Many studies have found neural activity in the hippocampus related to mathematical activity, but the scientific community has identified that activity as semantic processes for carrying out arithmetic fact retrieval (Supekar et al., 2013; Moeller et al., 2015; Menon, 2016; Kuhl et al., 2020; Menon and Chang, 2021). Menon and his colleagues have highlighted the contribution of hippocampal-prefrontal circuits to the early development of retrieval fluency in arithmetic problem-solving. In children, hippocampal-prefrontal and hippocampal-parietal connectivity have been associated

with the acquisition of retrieval-based solution strategies, whereas in adults hippocampal-parietal connectivity has been associated with the retrieval of arithmetic facts.

In contrast to the memory hypothesis regarding hippocampal formation activity, we intend to show that an alternative possibility exists for interpreting that activity. While we cannot deny that some neural activity registered in the hippocampus related to arithmetic operations could be caused by semantic memory processes, we consider that at least part, if not all, of the hippocampal activity is produced by the human brain using the navigational system to understand arithmetic facts and perform arithmetic calculations. Specifically, we address if the navigational system is able to allow understanding and calculating the following four kinds of arithmetic expressions:

- $x + y = z$ where x, y , and z are whole numbers.
- $x - y = z$ where x, y , and z are whole numbers.
- $x \times y = z$ where x, y , and z are whole numbers.
- $x \div y = z$ where x, y , and z are whole numbers.

To support the new interpretation of hippocampal activity, the first step is showing that the navigational system fulfills the three conditions listed above for determining whether a neural system is potentially capable of enabling the generation and understanding the operations that contain the four kinds of arithmetic expressions mentioned.

Evidence that the navigational system fulfils **C1** is provided in Section 3, as research has shown that the navigational system can create, store, and manipulate mental representations (Neupane et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2023; Widloski and Foster, 2022).

With regard to **C2**, the navigational system of the human brain fulfils it. The reason that **C2** is satisfied is that, as mentioned in Section 3.8, the navigational system allows a cognitive map to be recalled while an animal is sleeping and moves through it, a process called sleep replay (Foster and Wilson, 2007). Since it is known that when the brain is in the sleep state, the mental activity of the brain is not driven by sensory input because there is a strong inhibition of the signals sent by the senses (R.R. and Paré, 1991), the sleep replay phenomenon shows that the navigational system can be controlled volitionally. Also, the replay process does not happen only in the sleep state but also during the awake state (Kudrimoti et al., 1999; Jackson et al., 2006). Furthermore, recent investigations have shown that even rats have the ability to control the navigational system volitionally (Lai et al., 2023).

Evidence that the navigational system fulfils **C3** requires a mathematical proof, which is presented in the following subsection.

4.1 The navigational system allows endowing a semantic for arithmetic

Condition **C3** establishes that for a neuronal system to be able to understand arithmetic, it must create a mental representation and produce manipulations of it that match the true arithmetic statements. This condition is directly related to a question readers might have: how can navigation be related to arithmetic skills, or more specifically, how can a navigational system endow a semantic to the human brain to understand arithmetic? Although the reader could initially consider arithmetic and navigation to be completely disconnected, the possibility exists that those domains overlap to the extent that they are indistinguishable. Two domains are strongly interconnected, no matter how different the objects they contain, if for each object of a domain another object exists in the other domain so that the behavior of both objects is equivalent in its corresponding domain. In other words, two domains are equivalent if it is not possible to determine to which domain one object belongs when only its behavior is taken into account. If the navigational elements and arithmetical

objects are indistinguishable according to their behavior, the navigational system could be used to give meaning to arithmetic facts and understand arithmetic calculations. Therefore, to know whether **C3** is fulfilled, it is necessary to know until what point both domains overlap, because if they overlap completely, the navigational system emerges as a candidate neuronal system to advance resolving the SGPNC.

Some may question what it means to study whether navigation and arithmetic overlap. Given that the navigational system generates mental representations to describe the spatial features of an environment, this question refers to determining whether any numeric system of arithmetic is indistinguishable from a mental construct similar to a cognitive map. In the event that one numeric system is indistinguishable from a mental construct with the same features of a spatial representation, then that mental construct could be used to interpret numerical symbols and arithmetic operations of that numeric system. Otherwise, if a spatial representation that is indistinguishable from a numerical system did not exist, then the navigational system could not be used to understand arithmetic because it would cause the human brain to misjudge false arithmetic statements as true and true arithmetic statements as false.

Mathematically, the question of the similarity between two mathematical structures that belong to different domains is addressed by studying the existence of a morphism between both structures. A morphism is a function ¹ from one structure to another that establishes that certain characteristics of the objects of one structure are preserved by the objects of the other. When a structure is enough similar to the other, one can represent the other. This idea is used in advanced theoretical physics, e.g., the anti-de Sitter/conformal field theory correspondence (Maldacena, 1998). Thus, the question emerges whether a morphism from arithmetic to a spatial map exists that is similar enough to allow the human brain to use the navigational system to endow a semantic to arithmetic symbols and expressions. Addressing this question requires mathematical tools that have not yet been used in neuroscience but are indispensable for delving into this question and resolving it. Specifically, there are two branches of mathematics, universal algebra (or general algebra) and model theory, that study mathematical structures, and they contain the concepts and tools to reveal whether the navigational system is capable of providing the human brain with a semantic for understanding arithmetic. We will try to use those mathematical tools in the clearest way but we do not have space in this article to explain universal algebra and model theory, so readers interested in further details can find textbooks explaining these branches of mathematics (Burris and Sankappanavar, 1981; Manzano, 1999).

Arithmetic is a field of knowledge whose objects are nonphysical. In modern mathematics, the manner of studying arithmetic is to use algebraic structures that exist in its domain and formally describe its elements and features. An algebraic structure contains a set of elements with one or more operations defined in the set (operation is the specific name given to a function in some branches of mathematics). In studying arithmetic, the set is natural numbers, integers, or real numbers. To understand the degree of similarity between two mathematical structures, it is necessary to study the kinds of morphisms that can be defined between them, and the kind of morphism relevant for the question addressed here is isomorphism. Why is it relevant that the kind of morphism between both structures is an isomorphism in the problem that is being addressed? The reason is because an isomorphism between two mathematical structures means that one structure is a copy of the other, and it implies the two following important features. First, if there is an isomorphism h that preserves the mathematical structure, then the translation of any arithmetical claim that is true to the mental representation is also true in the mental representation,

¹The convention in the field of mathematics is to use the word function for an association of numbers from one number set with numbers of another set, but when the sets might not have numbers, the convention uses the word *map* instead of *function*. Since in the text *map* is used with the meaning it has in neuroscience, the word *function* will be used, even if the sets do not have numbers, to avoid possible confusion.

and the translation of any arithmetical claim that is false to the mental representation is also false in the mental representation. This feature would allow understanding any arithmetic fact. Second, if the morphism is an isomorphism, it also preserves the structure in the reverse direction. It implies that any true statement of the mental representation translated to the arithmetical language would also be a true arithmetic fact, and any false statement of the mental structure translated to the arithmetical language would be a false arithmetic fact too. Therefore, if the existence of an isomorphism is established, then it is plausible that the human brain could use the navigational system to generate and understand arithmetic knowledge. Figure 2 represents the idea of isomorphism graphically.

Figure 2: This figure is a graphical representation of the concept of isomorphism applied to geometric objects embedded in a metric space. With \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} being two geometrical objects, the existence of an isomorphism, \mathbf{h} , from one object to the other proves that both geometrical objects have the same shape and size and are oriented in the same direction. In this case, a morphism is a projection of each vertex of one of the geometrical objects. If \mathbf{h} projects each vertex of one of the objects applying the same direction and length and the result is each one of the vertices of the other geometrical object, then both geometrical objects are equal and oriented in the same direction.

For the previous reasons, proving that an isomorphism exists from arithmetic to a mental representation similar to a cognitive map is the key to answering whether the navigational system can be used as a mechanism to understand and produce arithmetic facts. In more mathematical language, the necessary question for determining whether the navigational system is able to allow human beings to understand arithmetic is formulated as follows: is there an isomorphism between arithmetic and any mental representation made by the navigational system?

At this point, the next issue to address is how we can know that an isomorphism exists from arithmetic to a cognitive map. Isomorphism is a question that has been extensively studied in all branches of mathematics. We are interested in how universal algebra addresses the question of define an isomorphism. If required, the reader may consult a briefly review of some concepts of universal algebra in the Appendix A. The following definition determines how we can establish mathematically when two algebras are isomorphic.

Given two algebras \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} of the same signature μ , a morphism \mathbf{h} from \mathcal{A} to \mathcal{B} is an isomorphism if it fulfils the following two conditions:

- 1) \mathbf{h} must be bijective (injective and exhaustive).
- 2) for every n-ary function f_i , and for $x_1, \dots, x_{\mu(i)} \in \mathcal{A}$; we have

$$f_i^{\mathcal{A}}(x_1, \dots, x_{\mu(i)}) = f_i^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{h}(x_1), \dots, \mathbf{h}(x_{\mu(i)}))$$

Therefore, if we find an algebra to represent arithmetic and another one to represent a mental representation made by the navigational system, we can study whether there is an isomorphism

between them checking the mentioned definition of isomorphism.

Once the previous question is answered, three issues emerge regarding proving the existence of an isomorphism between arithmetic and a cognitive map: I) What mathematical structure must be used to represent arithmetic? II) What class of mathematical structure describes mathematically the mental structures that are generated by the navigational system ? and III) What specific mental structure would the navigational-system use to endow a semantic for arithmetic? These three questions are addressed and answered below.

4.1.1 A mathematical structure to represent arithmetic

To address Question I, we should mention some issues regarding arithmetic. Arithmetic studies numerical operations and how they operate on different types of numbers. Arithmetic determines that the basic operations are addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. It also includes other operations, such as exponentiation, extraction of roots, and taking logarithms. In this article, we focus on the basic arithmetic operations on whole numbers. Whole numbers, denoted by \mathbb{N}_0 , include all natural numbers and 0, $\mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$. Each of the four basic arithmetic operations is used by one of the four kinds of arithmetic expressions that are the target of this investigation. We have selected those operations and whole numbers because those are the arithmetic skills first learned by children. Of the four basic operations, we begin with addition and subtraction.

The mathematical structure that describes the addition operation and the identity element in whole numbers has the signature $\langle \mathbb{N}_0; 0, + \rangle$. The addition operation is a 2-ary function, and a 0 is a 0-ary function (or constant). In whole numbers, the addition operation always returns a whole number, so it is a total function because it is defined for every pair of whole numbers. The domain and codomain of the addition operation is the following:

$$+ : \mathbb{N}_0 \times \mathbb{N}_0 \longrightarrow \mathbb{N}_0$$

Unlike addition, subtraction in whole numbers is a partial function because it is not defined when the minuend is smaller than the subtrahend, e.g., $2 - 5$ does not result in a whole number. The domain and codomain of the subtraction operation is defined in the following way:

$$- : \mathbb{N}_0 \times \mathbb{N}_0 \longrightarrow \mathbb{N}_0$$

Because the subtract function is a partial function on whole numbers, the concept of partial algebra is required (Burmeister, 1993). A partial algebra is a generalization of universal algebra that allows partial functions. Thus, we use \mathcal{A} to denote the mathematical structure with whole numbers and addition and subtraction. \mathcal{A} is a partial structure (because subtraction is a partial function) whose signature is $\langle \mathbb{N}_0, 0, +, - \rangle$. We could include multiplication and division operations to \mathcal{A} , but adding those operations would only lengthen the mathematical proofs, and because they will be addressed specifically in Section 4.1.8, their inclusion is unnecessary.

It is also important to keep in mind that arithmetic and algebra are different branches of mathematics. In this research, we address only how the human brain masters understanding arithmetic expressions and not how it achieves its capacity to understand the knowledge generated in the branch of algebra. From the point of view of evolutionary psychology, algebra belongs to a later stage than that of arithmetic in the mathematical development of human beings. Therefore, it is important to distinguish the problem of how the brain understands arithmetic from the problem of how it understands algebra.

4.1.2 A navigmap structure and its extensions

Question II asked which class of mathematical structure mathematically describes the kind of mental representations generated by the navigational system. To address this question, a new kind of mathematical structure, named navigmap, has been developed during the research process conducted for this article. A navigmap is a structure that mathematically describes the most fundamental features discovered in research on the navigational system in mammals. The first feature is that the navigational system is able to assign specific identifiers to specific locations, which is demonstrated by place cells, so the mathematical structure must have a domain of places (O’Keefe and Dostrovsky, 1971). The second feature is that the navigational system is able to determine directions, which is evident in the discovery of head-direction cells (Ranck Jr, 1984; Taube et al., 1990a,b), and this feature indicates that the structure must have a domain of directions. The third feature is that the navigational system is able to describe lengths of movement. This feature can be deduced from various discoveries, including that the hippocampus encodes distances between locations (Theves et al., 2019; Morgan et al., 2011) and that speed cells exist (Kropff et al., 2015; Spalla et al., 2022). Thus, the structure must have a domain of lengths of displacements. The fourth feature is that the navigational system assigns to a place of an environment the role of origin of coordinates. This feature is implied by the discovery that the navigational system of center-distance cells and center-bearing cells (Patrick A. LaChance, 2019). The fifth feature, that is directly related to the previous one, is that the navigational system allows estimating the distance and direction from a place to the origin of coordinates. This feature is derived from the discovery of center-distance cells and center-bearing cells (Patrick A. LaChance, 2019), and the fact that distance cells have been observed in the navigational system (Abramson et al., 2023). This feature also implies that an identifier for a place plays the role of an allocentric coordinate. The sixth feature is that the navigational system allows calculating the future place from a starting place after moving in a specific direction for a specific length with reference to the center of coordinates. This is a feature that everyone can experience for themselves. For example, people are able to imagine the environment in which they are immersed and predict their future position perfectly if they imagine starting from their current position and turning 90 degrees to the right and taking two steps forward. The seventh feature is that the navigational system allows calculating the direction and the distance between two places. This is also a feature that everyone can experience. For example, if people mentally select a place close to them, they can determine the direction and distance that connect both places. The eighth feature is that the navigational system allows determining a route from one place to another, and this feature is derived from experiments that show that the navigational system can calculate a route to achieve a place in a previously explored environment (Widloski and Foster, 2022). For that reason, the mathematical structure must have a function that generates a route.

In order to represent those seven features, a navigmap \mathfrak{N} is defined in the following way:

$$\mathfrak{N} = \langle \{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{L}, \}, \{put, loc, mft, ind, tracet\} \rangle$$

where the domains are the following:

- \mathbf{P} is a set named places.
- \mathbf{D} is a set named directions.
- \mathbf{L} is a totally ordered set named lengths.

A pair (d, l) where $d \in \mathbf{D}$ and $l \in \mathbf{L}$ is named indication, so the first element is a direction and the second is a length. The functions of the navigmap are the following:

- **put** is a function, named put function, that determines a specific place from the origin of coordinates. The function *put* takes an indication as the input, and the output is a place. If there is no place, the function returns the empty word, ϵ . The definition of its domain and codomain is as follows:

$$put : \mathbf{D} \times \mathbf{L} \longrightarrow \mathbf{P} \cup \{\epsilon\}$$

- **loc** is a function, named locate function, that returns the specific indication to go from the origin of coordinates to a specific place. The *loc* function takes the place as the input, and its output is an indication that points out where the place is situated with regard to the origin of coordinates. The definition of its domain and codomain is as follows:

$$loc : \mathbf{P} \longrightarrow \mathbf{D} \times \mathbf{L}$$

- The function *mft*, named move-from-toward function, determines at which place you will arrive when starting from one place and moving according to an indication. The definition of its domain and codomain is as follows:

$$mft : \mathbf{P} \times (\mathbf{D} \times \mathbf{L}) \longrightarrow \mathbf{P}$$

- *ind* is a function, named indicate function, that returns an indication to go from one place to another. The *ind* function takes two places as the input, and it returns an indication as the output. The definition of its domain and codomain is as follows:

$$ind : \mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{P} \longrightarrow \mathbf{D} \times \mathbf{L}$$

- The function *tracert* determines a route from one location to another one. The input of the function is two places, the origin place and the destination place, and the function returns all the places the route passes through. The definition of its domain and codomain is as follows:

$$tracert : \mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{P} \longrightarrow \mathbf{P}^*$$

where \mathbf{P}^* is the Kleene closure of \mathbf{P} . The Kleene closure in the definition of the function *tracert* describes the return as a sequence of places that forms a path from one place to another. If there is no path between two places, the function returns the empty word, ϵ .

Before continuing, we proceed to briefly introduce the technique of extension by definitions that can be used to generate an expansion to a specific mathematical structure. In model theory, a mathematical structure is described using a formal language. Each mathematical structure has a formal language associated with it. The symbols of the signature of a mathematical structure are the alphabet of the adequate language for that mathematical structure. The technique of extension by definition formalizes the introduction of new non-logical symbols (e.g., functions) in a language adequate for a mathematical structure (Manzano, 1999). Therefore, given a signature τ , it is possible to generate another signature τ' where $\tau \subseteq \tau'$ using the technique of extension by definition. Using τ' , a new theory T' can be generated, adding new formulas that contain the non-logical symbols of τ' . Using T' , a τ' -structure \mathfrak{U}' , can be generated in accordance with Lindenbaum's lemma and Henkin's lemma (Manzano, 1999). In this way, a τ' -structure \mathfrak{U}' can be generated by starting from τ -structure \mathfrak{U} , and \mathfrak{U}' is a model of a T' . When that situation happens, we say that \mathfrak{U}' is a definitional expansion of \mathfrak{U} . Abramson2023

The proof of isomorphism that the problem being addressed here requires entails finding a

mathematical structure with functions that are equivalent to the operations that exist in arithmetic. The technique of extension by definition is relevant for finding that mathematical structure because it allows generating new mathematical structures based on \mathfrak{N} making explicit functions that are implicit in \mathfrak{N} . For example, we can extend the signature of a standard navigmap, η , by adding new functions by definition, and generate another signature η' . Specifically, we define an extension by definitions of η by adding a new function, *merge*. The function *merge* takes two indications as the input, and it returns an indication. Therefore, the definition of its domain and codomain is as follows:

$$\text{merge} : (\mathbf{D} \times \mathbf{L}) \times (\mathbf{D} \times \mathbf{L}) \longrightarrow \mathbf{L} \cup \{\epsilon\}$$

The function uses the first indication to calculate a place from the origin of coordinates, and it uses the second indication to calculate a new place from the place generated with the first indication. If there is no place, the function returns the empty word, ϵ . Thus, *merge* can be defined in the following way:

$$\text{merge}((d, l_x), (d', l_y)) = \pi_2^2(\text{loc}(\text{mft}(\text{put}(d, l_x)), (d', l_y)))$$

where π_2^2 is the projection function that extracts the second element from an ordered pair.

As a consequence of *merge* being defined, we extend η and generate $\eta' = \{\text{put}, \text{loc}, \text{mft}, \text{ind}, \text{tracert}, \text{merge}\}$. Using η' , we obtain \mathfrak{N}' , which is an η' -structure.

$$\mathfrak{N}' = \langle \{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{L}, \}, \{\text{put}, \text{loc}, \text{mft}, \text{ind}, \text{tracert}, \text{merge}\} \rangle$$

Question III asks which mental spatial representation the navigational system would use to endow a semantic for arithmetic in whole numbers. The answer is a mental representation describing an environment whose shape is a straight line, that is, a one-dimensional space. The reason is that from a formal point of view, whole numbers (non-negative integers) are geometrically described as points on a straight line or as a one-dimensional space. A straight-line shape is much simpler than the geometry of real-world environments, so the navigational system is powerful enough to represent it. Also, we know that the mammal navigational system can build a map of a one-dimensional space because experiments studying the navigational system have been conducted by placing animals in an environment whose shape was a line or a concatenation of straight segments.

Once it is determined that a one-dimensional cognitive map is the kind of mental representation from the navigational system that must be verified, the next step is defining which specific mathematical structure that describes a one-dimensional spatial mental representation must be used in the mathematical study to check for the existence of an isomorphism. Here, we have mentioned that we are interested in whole numbers, so we have to study the existence of an isomorphism that requires a navigmap.

The mathematical structure employed to study an isomorphism with whole numbers is denoted by $\mathfrak{N}_{\rightarrow}$ where $\mathfrak{N}_{\rightarrow}$ is defined in the following way:

$$\mathfrak{N}_{\rightarrow} = \langle \{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{L}, \}, \{\text{put}, \text{loc}, \text{mft}, \text{ind}, \text{tracert}\} \rangle$$

where

- $\mathbf{P} = \{\mathbf{p}_i : i \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$
- $\mathbf{D} = \{\rightarrow, \leftarrow\}$
- $\mathbf{L} = (\{\mathbf{l}_j : j \in \mathbb{N}_0\})$

The origin of coordinates is fixed at the element \mathbf{p}_0 of the set \mathbf{P} . The set \mathbf{D} has only two elements because it is a one-dimensional space and only two possible directions exist. The set \mathbf{L} does not contain negative elements and \mathbf{l}_0 represents length 0.

The functions of the navigmap are the following:

- **put** is defined in the following way:

$$put(d, \mathbf{l}_x) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{p}_x & , \text{ if } d = \rightarrow \\ \epsilon & , \text{ if } d = \leftarrow \end{cases}$$

- **loc** is defined in the following way:

$$loc(\mathbf{p}_x) = (\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_x)$$

- **mft** is defined in the following way:

$$mft(P_x, (d, \mathbf{l}_y)) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{l}_{(x+y)} & , \text{ if } d = \rightarrow \\ \mathbf{l}_{(x-y)} & , \text{ if } d = \leftarrow \quad \wedge \quad \wedge \quad l_x \succeq l_y \\ \epsilon & , \text{ if } d = \leftarrow \quad \wedge \quad \wedge \quad l_x \prec l_y \end{cases}$$

- **ind** is defined in the following way:

$$ind(p_x, p_y) = \begin{cases} (\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_{|l-y|}) & , \text{ if } x > y \\ (\leftarrow, \mathbf{l}_{|l-y|}) & , \text{ if } x < y \\ (\rightarrow, \mathbf{0}) & , \text{ if } x = y \end{cases}$$

- **tracert** is defined in the following way:

$$tracert(p_x, p_y) = \begin{cases} (p_x, p_{x-1}, p_{x-2}, \dots, p_y) & , \text{ if } x > y \\ (p_x, p_{x+1}, p_{x+2}, \dots, p_y) & , \text{ if } x < y \\ (p_x) & , \text{ if } x = y \end{cases}$$

As was mentioned, we can define *merge* in the following way:

$$merge((d, l_x), (d', l_y)) = \pi_2^2(loc(mft(put(d, l)), (d', l_y)))$$

Thus, we can expand $\mathfrak{N}_{\rightarrow}$ to generate $\mathfrak{N}'_{\rightarrow}$, whose signature is η'_{\rightarrow} , which includes *merge* in the set of function symbols.

It is interesting to note that D has only two elements, \rightarrow and \leftarrow , and using the parameter theorem (also called s-m-n theorem) (Nies, 2009), we can obtain different functions from *merge* as a result of fixing d_1 and d_2 . Consequently, we denote $merge^+$ and $merge^-$ to the functions:

$$merge^+(\mathbf{l}_x, \mathbf{l}_y) = merge((\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_x), (\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_y))$$

and

$$merge^-(\mathbf{l}_x, \mathbf{l}_y) = merge((\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_x), (\leftarrow, \mathbf{l}_y))$$

The structure $\langle \mathbb{N}_0, 0, +, - \rangle$ is smaller than $\mathfrak{N}'_{\rightarrow}$. Therefore, to answer the question of whether the navigational system is able to endow a semantic for arithmetic, it is necessary to study whether it is

possible to define a morphism that is an isomorphism between mathematical structure $\langle \mathbb{N}_0, 0, +, - \rangle$ and a part of \mathfrak{N}'_{\mapsto} . The part of \mathfrak{N}'_{\mapsto} is also a mathematical structure, denoted by \mathfrak{M} , that has a subsignature of η'_{\mapsto} , which we denote by $\eta^{\mathfrak{M}}_{\mapsto}$. The signature $\eta^{\mathfrak{M}}_{\mapsto}$ is the following:

$$\eta^{\mathfrak{M}}_{\mapsto} = \langle \mathbf{l}_0, merge^+, merge^- \rangle$$

where \mathbf{l}_0 is an 0-ary function and $merge^+$ and $merge^-$ are 2-ary functions. The structure \mathfrak{M} is hereby defined as:

$$\mathfrak{M} = \langle \mathbf{L}; \mathbf{l}_0, merge^+, merge^- \rangle$$

where $\mathbf{L}, \mathbf{l}_0, merge^+$, and $merge^-$ are the same elements found in \mathfrak{N}'_{\mapsto} .

This article focuses on the skill of performing arithmetic calculations with whole numbers, so we study the existence of an isomorphism, \mathbf{h} , between the partial structures \mathcal{A} and \mathfrak{M} . As was mentioned, an isomorphism between two algebras requires proving that it fulfills two conditions: 1) \mathbf{h} is bijective, and 2) every arithmetic operation is equivalent to a navigation operation movement in the corresponding navigmap. We address the task of proving both conditions below. The proofs are written using function notation instead of infix notation.

4.1.3 \mathbf{h} is bijective

First, the morphism \mathbf{h} between the two mathematical structures is defined. The morphism \mathbf{h} is defined in the following way for each one of the sorts:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h} : \mathbb{N}_0 &\longrightarrow \mathbf{L} \\ x &\mapsto \mathbf{l}_x \end{aligned}$$

Now, the following lemma is going to be proven:

Lemma 4.1. $\mathbf{h} : \mathbb{N}_0 \longrightarrow \mathbf{L}$ is bijective.

It is known that a function is bijective if and only if it has an inverse function. We prove that \mathbf{h}' is the inverse of \mathbf{h} by showing that the composition of \mathbf{h} with \mathbf{h}' generates the identity function for the set $\mathbb{N}_0, \mathbf{i}_{\mathbb{N}_0}$, and the composition of \mathbf{h}' with \mathbf{h} generates the identity function for the set L, \mathbf{i}_L .

Proof. Given \mathbf{h}' , where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}' : \mathbf{L} &\longrightarrow \mathbb{N}_0 \\ \mathbf{l}_x &\mapsto x \end{aligned}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}'(\mathbf{h}(x)) &= \\ \mathbf{h}'(\mathbf{l}_x) &= \\ &= x \end{aligned}$$

therefore,

$$\mathbf{h} \circ \mathbf{h}' = \mathbf{i}_{\mathbb{N}}$$

and also,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{h}'(\mathbf{l}_x)) &= \\ \mathbf{h}(x) &= \\ &= \mathbf{l}_x \end{aligned}$$

therefore,

$$\mathbf{h}' \circ \mathbf{h} = \mathbf{i}_P$$

Therefore, \mathbf{h}' is the inverse, \mathbf{h}^{-1} , of h , and that implies that \mathbf{h} is bijective.

QED

4.1.4 Addition operation

Once it has been proven that h is bijective, it is necessary to prove that every arithmetical operation with whole numbers can be carried out by the functions that \mathfrak{M} has. Now, we address whether the addition operation has its equivalent in $\mathfrak{N}_{\rightarrow}^{\circ}$. Specifically, we focus on the operation $merge^+$. The intuitive idea of the proof is to show that addition is equivalent to moving to the right in a line. Previous to that, it is necessary to bear in mind that the $merge$ function has two inputs of the same kind, but the first input parameter is used to localize a place from the origin of coordinates, and the second parameter is used to localize a new place from the place calculated with the first input. The origin of coordinates is fixed at p_0 .

Lemma 4.2. $+ is equivalent to merge^+.$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}(+(a, b)) &= merge^+(\mathbf{h}(a), \mathbf{h}(b)) \\ \mathbf{h}(+(a, b)) &= merge^+(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b) \\ \mathbf{h}(+(a, b)) &= merge((\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_a), (\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_b)) \\ \mathbf{h}(+(a, b)) &= \pi_2^2(loc(mft(put(\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_a), (\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_b))) \\ \mathbf{h}(+(a, b)) &= \pi_2^2(loc(mft(\mathbf{p}_a), (\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_b))) \\ \mathbf{h}(+(a, b)) &= \pi_2^2(loc(\mathbf{p}_{a+b}) \\ \mathbf{h}(+(a, b)) &= \pi_2^2(\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_{a+b}) \\ \mathbf{h}(+(a, b)) &= \mathbf{l}_{a+b} \\ \mathbf{l}_{a+b} &= \mathbf{l}_{a+b} \end{aligned}$$

QED

In the Appendix B, we prove commutativity and the addition of $merge^+$.

4.1.5 Subtraction operation

Intuitively, the idea of the proof is that subtraction is equivalent to moving to the left in a line. Thus, we address whether the subtraction operation has its equivalent in \mathfrak{M} . Specifically, we focus on the operation $merge^-$. Since subtraction is a partial function in whole numbers, we consider two cases: $x \geq y$ and $x < y$.

Lemma 4.3. $- is equivalent to merge^-.$

Proof. Case $a \geq b$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}(-(a, b)) &= merge^-(\mathbf{h}(a), \mathbf{h}(b)) \\ \mathbf{h}(-(a, b)) &= merge^-(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b) \\ \mathbf{h}(-(a, b)) &= merge((\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_a), (\leftarrow, \mathbf{l}_b)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{h}(-(a, b)) &= \pi_2^2(\text{loc}(\text{mft}(\text{put}(\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_a), (\leftarrow, \mathbf{l}_b)))) \\
\mathbf{h}(-(a, b)) &= \pi_2^2(\text{loc}(\text{mft}(\mathbf{p}_a), (\leftarrow, \mathbf{l}_b))) \\
\mathbf{h}(-(a, b)) &= \pi_2^2(\text{loc}(\mathbf{p}_{a-b})) \\
\mathbf{h}(-(a, b)) &= \pi_2^2(\leftarrow, \mathbf{l}_{a-b}) \\
\mathbf{h}(-(x, y)) &= \mathbf{l}_{x-y} \\
l_{x-y} &= l_{x-y}
\end{aligned}$$

Case $a < b$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{h}(-(x, y)) &= \text{merge}^-(\mathbf{h}(x), \mathbf{h}(y)) \\
\mathbf{h}(-(x, y) \uparrow) &= \text{merge}^-(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b) \\
\mathbf{h}(-(a, b) \uparrow) &= \text{merge}^-(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b) \\
\mathbf{h}(-(a, b) \uparrow) &= \text{merge}((\rightarrow, \mathbf{l}_a), (\leftarrow, \mathbf{l}_b)) \uparrow
\end{aligned}$$

QED

In addition, we can check that merge^- does not have the commutative and associative property that happens with $-$.

We can check that merge^- is non-commutative using merge^- 's own definition. If $a < b$, then $\text{merge}^-(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b)$ is undefined and $\text{merge}^-(\mathbf{l}_b, \mathbf{l}_a)$ is defined. In the opposite case, if $a > b$, then $\text{merge}^-(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b)$ is defined and $\text{merge}^-(\mathbf{l}_b, \mathbf{l}_a)$ is undefined.

This proves that the subtraction operation is equivalent to a navigation operation movement and also that any movement with mft^\rightarrow can be interpreted as a subtraction operation.

4.1.6 Identity elements

In the structure \mathcal{A} , there is one constant: the identity element. The identity element is a two-sided identity, which means it is a left identity and a right identity at the same time. We start by addressing the morphism from \mathcal{A} and \mathfrak{M} structures that satisfies that the $\mathbf{h}(0)$ is a left identity. The assignation done by \mathbf{h} is the following:

$$\mathbf{h} : 0 \mapsto \mathbf{l}_0$$

According to the previous association, the following claim emerges:

Lemma 4.4. *0 is equivalent to \mathbf{l}_0 , each being a left identity in its respective structure.*

Now, we prove that \mathbf{l}_0 fulfills the condition of being a left identity for addition and subtraction.

Proof. The condition of being a left identity using the many-sorted formulation is the following:

$$\forall a, b \in \mathbb{N}_0, a = 0 \rightarrow +(a, b) = b$$

if we apply \mathbf{h}

$$\forall \mathbf{h}(a), \mathbf{h}(b) \in \mathbf{h}(\mathbb{N}_0), \mathbf{h}(a) = \mathbf{h}(0) \rightarrow \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(a), (b)) = \mathbf{h}(b)$$

and after obtaining the image of each element, we obtain the following:

$$\forall \mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b \in \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{l}_a = \mathbf{l}_0 \rightarrow merge^+(\mathbf{l}_0, \mathbf{l}_b) = \mathbf{h}(b)$$

This previous condition can be used to verify that \mathbf{l}_0 is a left identity. However, it is not necessary because in the subtraction of a pair of numbers, a and b , $-(a,b)$, when x is the left identity, the result is only defined when $b = 0$ for whole numbers because if a is the left identity and $b > 0$, the subtraction operation is not defined, $-(0, b) \uparrow$. Given the definition of the function $merge^-$, $merge^-(\mathbf{l}_0, \mathbf{l}_b) \uparrow$, when $0 < b$. Therefore, to prove that the subtraction operation is isomorphic, it is sufficient to $merge^-$ with the pair $(0, 0)$.

$$\mathbf{h}(-(0, 0)) = merge^-(\mathbf{h}(0, 0))$$

$$\mathbf{h}(0) = merge^-(\mathbf{l}_0, \mathbf{l}_0)$$

$$\mathbf{l}_0 = \mathbf{l}_{0-0}$$

$$\mathbf{l}_0 = \mathbf{l}_0$$

This shows that, considering that subtraction is a partial function in whole numbers, the morphism h holds the structure with regard to the left identity.

QED

Now we check that \mathbf{l}_0 is a right identity. According to the association done by \mathbf{h} , the following claim is formulated:

Lemma 4.5. *0 is equivalent to \mathbf{l}_0 , each being a right identity in its respective structure.*

Now, we prove that \mathbf{l}_0 fulfills the condition of being a right identity for addition and subtraction.

Proof. The condition of being a right identity is the following:

$$\forall a, b \in \mathbb{N}_0, \quad b = 0 \rightarrow +(a, b) = a$$

if we apply \mathbf{h}

$$\forall \mathbf{h}(a), \mathbf{h}(b) \in \mathbf{h}(\mathbb{N}_0), \mathbf{h}(b) = \mathbf{h}(0) \rightarrow merge^+(\mathbf{h}(a), (b)) = \mathbf{h}(a)$$

and after obtaining the image of each element we obtain the following:

$$\forall \mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b \in \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{l}_a = \mathbf{l}_0 \rightarrow merge^+(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_0) = \mathbf{h}(a)$$

$$\forall \mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b \in \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{l}_a = \mathbf{l}_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{l}_{a+0} = \mathbf{h}(a)$$

The result agrees with the definition of right identity with regard to the addition operation.

Finally, we check the right identity regarding the subtraction operation.

$$\forall a, b \in \mathbb{N}_0, \quad b = 0 \rightarrow -(a, b) = a$$

if we apply \mathbf{h}

$$\forall \mathbf{h}(a), \mathbf{h}(b) \in \mathbf{h}(\mathbb{N}_0), \mathbf{h}(b) = \mathbf{h}(0) \rightarrow merge^-(\mathbf{h}(a), (b)) = \mathbf{h}(a)$$

and after obtaining the image of each element, we obtain the following condition:

$$\forall \mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b \in \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{l}_b = \mathbf{l}_0 \rightarrow \text{merge}^-(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_0) = \mathbf{h}(a)$$

Using the previous condition, we can verify that \mathbf{l}_0 is a right identity.

$$\mathbf{h}(-(a, 0)) = \text{merge}^-(\mathbf{h}(a), \mathbf{h}(0))$$

$$\mathbf{h}(a) = \text{merge}^-(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_0)$$

$$\mathbf{l}_a = \mathbf{l}_{a-0}$$

$$\mathbf{l}_a = \mathbf{l}_a$$

The result agrees with the definition of right identity with regard to the subtraction operation.

QED

4.1.7 \mathbf{h} is an isomorphism

Theorem 4.6. *Given $\mathcal{A} = \langle \mathbb{N}_0; 0, +, - \rangle$ and $\mathfrak{M} = \langle \mathbf{L}; \mathbf{l}_0, \text{merge}^+, \text{merge}^- \rangle$, there exists an isomorphism \mathbf{h} between them, $\mathbf{h} : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathfrak{M}$.*

Proof. Taking Lemma 4.1, Lemma 4.2, Lemma 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5, it is proven that \mathbf{h} is an isomorphism between \mathcal{A} and \mathfrak{M} . QED

After finishing the proof of the isomorphism, the reader could be worried that the proof involves the existence of infinite place cells, which is obviously a premise that is not fulfilled by the human brain. It is true that the proof assumes infinite place cells, but it does not affect the relevance of the proof because there are three facts that justify why the proof is useful and valuable despite the assumption of a premise that is not biologically correct.

The first fact to consider is that the proof that h is an isomorphism shows that the navigational system can provide tools to understand and generate arithmetic calculations on whole numbers. The second fact to bear in mind is that although humans have the concept of infinity and it is known that there are infinite whole numbers, the human brain is limited in the numbers it can think of because there is a limit to the length of a number that the human brain can conceive of. Beyond that limit, the human brain is unable to remember, manipulate, or compare numbers of that length. That is to say, the capacity of the human brain to mentally represent numbers is limited, and something that the brain is not able to do cannot be argued as a reason to reject that the navigational system is involved in the understanding and generating of arithmetic statements. The last fact that explains why the proof is meaningful is that the human brain only requires a small set of numbers to perform arithmetic calculations with large numbers since the positional notation allows breaking any number (e.g., 524 is five hundreds, two tens, and four units), and this fact involves only the need to perform single-digit calculations for each digit of the two numbers being used in any addition or subtraction operation. In other words, a finite number of place cells would be sufficient for performing calculations with large numbers because of the positional notation. In fact, it is known that human beings use different strategies when they are trying to resolve small and large problems (Zbrodoff and Logan, 2005). Therefore, the human brain only requires that the navigational system be able to address small arithmetic problems to endow a semantic to ground arithmetic symbols.

It is important to highlight that although the sort of the domain and codomain of the functions merge^+ and merge^- are only based on \mathbf{L} , under those functions there is a hidden machinery that carries out the calculations. In that machinery, the functions *put*, *loc*, and *mft* that use sorts that represent direction cells and place cells are very relevant. Another important issue regarding the

proof is that the signature of the $\mathfrak{N}_{\rightarrow}$ structure can be interpreted as a kind of neural architecture. Although the signature of $\mathfrak{N}_{\rightarrow}$ has been established by considering several facts discovered by research on the navigational system, the knowledge about how the navigational system works in humans is far from complete. It cannot be ruled out that another kind of mathematical structure represents the neural architecture of the navigational system of the human brain better than the class of structures determined by $\mathfrak{N}_{\rightarrow}$. Despite this fact, it does not affect the proof because any other alternative navigmap structure must allow navigating through an environment by its own definition; this implies that an isomorphism proof could also be created for that alternative navigmap structure. Thus, the relevant issue that the isomorphism proof highlights is that navigation is a substrate to ground arithmetical operations.

A last question that the reader could be thinking about the proof is why $\mathfrak{N}_{\rightarrow}$ has been defined with the signature presented. If the reader considers the possibility that other mathematical structures exist, we confirm that other mathematical structures with a different signature could be defined to describe the process of generating a spatial representation of an environment and paths of navigation. Given this fact, the answer to why the signature presented has been selected among all the possibilities is that Occam's Razor has been applied by selecting the structure that provides the least complex proof of isomorphism and therefore the least complex explanation.

Based on the proof and facts provided above, it is concluded that, from a mathematical point of view, the navigational system is able to allow the human brain to understand and generate arithmetical calculations with whole numbers.

4.1.8 Multiplication and division operations

Another important question that readers might consider is that this paper has only explained how two of the basic mathematical operations can be grounded but not how multiplication and division operations can be grounded. Although it is true that humans learn multiplication tables as facts, they are also able to provide explanations — for example, humans can say that $2 \times 3 = 6$ is true and $2 \times 3 = 8$ is false, and if they have a good command of arithmetic, they are able to explain why the first statement is true and the other is false. To address these questions, it is necessary to understand what the multiplication operation is exactly. The definition of the multiplication operation, denoted by \times , is as follows:

$$\text{multiplier} \times \text{multiplicand} = \text{product}$$

The meaning of the two operands in the multiplication operation are “multiplicand,” which is the number we are multiplying, and “multiplier,” which is the number we multiply by. The operation of multiplication can be interpreted as a repetition of sums in which the multiplicand is summed to itself the number of times indicated by the multiplier. Multiplication can be broken down into a more fundamental element, addition. Thus, the following equivalence shows how multiplication can be defined using addition:

$$\text{multiplier} \times \text{multiplicand} = \overbrace{\text{multiplicand} + \cdots + \text{multiplicand}}^{\text{multiplier}}.$$

Using that fact, the multiplication of two whole numbers, $n \times m$, could be grounded by the navigational system in the following way:

$$n \times m \equiv \overbrace{\text{merge}^+(\cdots \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{l}_0, \mathbf{l}_m) \cdots)}^n \mathbf{l}_m$$

Consequently, the multiplication operation is grounded in the addition operation, and the navigational system would therefore be able to explain how the human brain gives meaning to the multiplication operation and the arithmetic statements it involves.

The last basic arithmetic operation remaining to be addressed is the division operation, denoted by \div . The division operation has four operands: dividend, divisor, quotient, and remainder. The quotient is the number of times that the divisor number goes into the dividend. The remainder is the part of the dividend that is left over from the number of times that the divisor goes into the dividend.

$$\text{Dividend} \div \text{Divisor} = \text{Quotient}$$

$$\text{Dividend} \bmod \text{Divisor} = \text{Remainder}$$

where

$$\text{Dividend} = \text{Divisor} \times \text{Quotient} + \text{Remainder}$$

Just as multiplication can be reduced to another operation, division can be reduced to another operation, which in this case is subtraction.

$$\text{Dividend} - \overbrace{\text{Divisor} - \dots - \text{Divisor}}^{\text{Quotient}} = \text{Remainder}$$

Using that fact, the division of two whole numbers, $a \div b$, could be grounded by the navigational system in the following way:

$$a \div b = q \quad \equiv \quad \overbrace{\text{merge}^{-}(\dots \text{merge}^{-}(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b) \dots)}^q \mathbf{l}_b$$

$$a \bmod b = r \quad \equiv \quad \overbrace{\text{merge}^{-}(\dots \text{merge}^{-}(\mathbf{l}_a, \mathbf{l}_b) \dots)}^q \mathbf{l}_b = \mathbf{l}_r$$

Consequently, the division operation is grounded in the subtraction operation, and the navigational system would therefore be able to explain how the human brain gives meaning to the subtraction operation and arithmetic statements that it involves.

It is interesting to note that grounding multiplication and division operations make use of working memory since it is necessary to count the number of navigational operations.

4.2 The numeric map principle

According to the facts presented, the navigational system fulfills the three conditions previously established for determining the plausibility that a neural system is able to allow generating and understanding arithmetic statements. Specifically, it is worth noting that the navigational system has enough power to endow a semantic to the human brain for the four kinds of arithmetic expressions because it can yield a mental representation that is isomorphic to the whole numbers and the addition and subtraction operations. After clarifying the previous issues, we present a formalization of the starting hypothesis, the numeric map principle, that claims the following:

The numeric map principle (NMP). *The human brain is able to use its navigational system to create a type of mental construct, called a numeric map, that is isomorphic to a fragment of the arithmetic. Using the replay process that the navigational system possesses on the numeric map, the human brain can understand and generate arithmetic statements. The human brain is able to ground addition and subtraction operations directly to fundamental navigational operations. The other two basic arithmetical operations, multiplication and division, are able to ground to addition*

and subtraction; *i.e.*, multiplication can be grounded as a repetition of addition, division can be grounded as a repetition of subtraction.

The process detailed in the NMP that encodes one domain in the domain of another system might sound strange in the field of neuroscience because a nervous system usually has a specific system to process each kind of information from the environment. However, the definition of an encoding function to transfer a calculation from one domain to another is a common technique in theoretical computer science. The technique of encoding the elements of one domain in another is used for different purposes. One purpose is for measuring the computational power of a model of computation and comparing the computational power of two different models of computation. Each computational model has its own set of states, which makes it difficult to know and compare the computational power of each system. The definition of encoding functions resolves this problem by encoding the positive integers in the set of states of the model of computation and using the encoding to determine the set of functions on the positive integers that can be calculated by each model of computation. Once the set of functions that can be calculated by each model of computation is determined, the only step that remains is to compare the sets associated with the different computational models to know which has more computational power.

Another purpose for which an encoding technique can be used is carrying out numerical calculations using a specific model of computation. In fact, people use the encoding/decoding approach when they use digital devices. For example, if someone wants to know the result of a numerical function for a specific input that requires many calculations, they can use a digital device to calculate it. Thus, if someone determines a result using a personal computer, it requires one function to encode the numerical input, another function to decode the string output and the algorithm which is equivalent to the concerned numerical function to be calculated. From a mathematical point of view, if one assumes the Turing machine as the model of computation that represents the digital device, the encoding/decoding approach to calculate the output produced by a numerical function can be expressed equationally in the following way:

$$\text{For all } n \in \mathbb{N} \quad \beta^{-1}(M_f(\beta(n))) = f(n)$$

where \mathbb{N} is the set of positive integers, β is a coding function, β^{-1} is a decoding function, and M_f is the Turing machine that is equivalent to the function f .

The encoding/decoding technique is usually represented using a commutative diagram. The commutative diagram of the mentioned example is Diagram 4.2.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathbb{B}^\omega & \xrightarrow{M_f} & \mathbb{B}^\omega \\ \uparrow \beta & & \downarrow \beta^{-1} \\ \mathbb{N} & \xrightarrow{f} & \mathbb{N} \end{array}$$

where \mathbb{B}^ω is the set of infinite binary words.

Precisely, it is the second use case of the encoding technique just explained that the human brain would take advantage of in a preexisting system to achieve a neural system that provides a deep understanding of arithmetic knowledge, avoiding the need for incorporating a dedicated system in the brain to do so. Thus, the isomorphisms \mathbf{h} and \mathbf{h}^{-1} defined in mathematical proof presented show that it is possible to define the encoding and decoding functions that allow the human brain to use the navigational system to ground arithmetic symbols.

One prediction that emerges from the NMP and the mathematical proof presented is that while a human being is doing mental arithmetic, the activity of single neuron cells in the navigational

system is tuned to a specific number. We name those neurons number cells. This prediction is derived from the fact that the domains L and P are part of the mathematical structure used to describe the navigational system. Although the method used by the navigational system to encode distances in its neuronal activity, the elements of L , is not yet clear, we know that the places of an environment are encoded by place cells, which are represented by the elements of P . Since each element of P represents a numeric cell and a number, numeric cells in the navigational system would be the underlying mechanism in the brain for grounding the meaning for numbers. Figure 3 explains graphically the main idea formulated in the NMP. We address the prediction of numeric cells in the navigational system in Subsection 4.3.1.

Figure 3: This figure presents the main concepts involved in the NMP. A) This figure shows the number line. It is a geometrical representation of the whole numbers used to teach arithmetic to children. B) This figure shows how the navigational system in mammals activates place cells in the CA1 layer to determine its location in a spatial representation of an environment. The dots indicate the positions where action potentials are recorded in an environment whose shape is a tube, with the colors indicating which neuron emitted that action potential. C) The NMP proposes that the navigation system is used to understand arithmetic statements, which would result in the CA1 layer of the human brain having neurons tuned to numbers. The dots indicate the numbers where action potentials should be recorded, with the colors indicating which neuron emitted that action potential. We denominate those neurons number cells.

It is important to note that the NMP does not state that a numeric map is the only mechanism or strategy to make or understand numbers and arithmetic. Mathematical cognitive development consists of different stages, and in children the acquisition of a numeric map would be an advanced stage in which arithmetic has been interiorized against previous stages, such as those in which children perform operations by counting with their fingers. Thus, it is important to highlight that if the NMP is true, a navigational map is not an innate mental structure, but one that is actively formed. This topic is discussed in more depth in the next section.

The NMP points to a neuronal system that generates and understands arithmetical statements,

and it also provides a new interpretation of the neural activity related to mental arithmetic observed in the hippocampal formation. According to the NMP, understanding basic arithmetic operations emerges from the navigational system. Therefore, the substratum of the semantic that human beings possess for interpreting arithmetic operations would be the structures of the hippocampal formation and other structures related to navigation, such as the parahippocampal cortex. Research on the navigational system and the function of the neurons that compose it is key to interpreting the neural activity observed in the human brain during arithmetical calculations and to understanding what the brain is doing.

Activity registered in the hippocampus has always been considered a consequence of memory-related processes (Moeller et al., 2015). However, the NMP proposes an alternative interpretation of this neural activity to understand how the human brain carries out arithmetical skills, breaking with the previous view by proposing that the activity is related to using the navigational system. We discuss this issue in more detail in Section 5.

4.3 Evidence supporting the numeric map principle

Now that the NMP has been formulated and discussed, we present facts that are consistent with and support the NMP. Several of the facts mentioned below had been previously interpreted as neural activity reflecting the performance of arithmetic knowledge retrieval and storage processes; however, the NMP aligns with and provides a new explanation for these facts that we consider to be better than the retrieval hypothesis. We also discuss in Subsection 5.2 the advantages of the NMP over the memory retrieval hypothesis in explaining activity in the hippocampal formation. We group this evidence into four categories: neuronal activity registered in basic neuroscience research, neural activity in mathematical cognitive development, cognitive techniques in the learning of arithmetic skills, and pathologies that involve the hippocampal formation.

4.3.1 Neuronal activity registered in basic neuroscience research

Given that the NMP provides a new mechanism for how the human brain understands arithmetical calculations, the search for evidence supporting the NMP has begun by focusing on studies that have registered neural activity in the hippocampal formation related to mental arithmetic.

- **Number cells in the hippocampus.** According to the NMP, single cells, which we have named number cells, that respond to symbolic and non-symbolic numerosities must exist in the hippocampus to perform arithmetical calculations, and they should be detectable when a subject carries out arithmetical calculations. The existence of this kind of cell is derived from the existence of place cells in the navigational system. If the NMP is true, number cells must exist because they play the same role in a number map that place cells play in a cognitive map. In reviewing the literature, we identified an investigation which carried out recordings from single neurons in neurology patients while they were performing arithmetic operations; the recordings identified neurons tuned to specific numbers in the hippocampus (Kutter et al., 2018). Those neurons match with the number cells predicted by NMP, making this finding key evidence that supports the NMP. Also, the existence of number cells explains why it has been impossible to decode result of additions in cortical areas Pinheiro-Chagas et al. (2019).
- **Entorhinal and parahippocampal cortex activity.** Navigational research has shown that the parahippocampal and entorhinal cortex are involved in navigation and path planning. In accordance with the NMP, arithmetical operations consist of carrying out a displacement across the numeric map. Therefore, if the NMP is correct, entorhinal and parahippocampal cortex activity must be registered when a human subject performs addition and subtraction

operations. In a study that obtained recordings from single neurons in neurology patients, the investigators observed activity that contains information about arithmetical calculations in the entorhinal and parahippocampal cortex activity. This is very important evidence of the NMP (Kutter et al., 2022).

- **Context change in the hippocampus.** One of the functions of the navigational system is to change the context so that an organism can plan routes when changing from one environment to another. Changing the context involves activating a specific cognitive map according to the environment in which the organism is located. The phenomenon of change of context is known as remapping, which was mentioned in Section 3. The NMP claims that the navigational system of the human brain creates a numeric map. Because a numeric map would be a mental representation built and handled by the navigational system like a cognitive map, a numeric map should be also affected by the process of remapping like a cognitive map. Thus, there should be performance differences in resolving simple arithmetical problems between individuals for whom a remapping previously occurred that activated a numeric map and for those for whom the remapping occurs when the arithmetic problem is presented to them. This difference would emerge because if the remapping happened before the presentation of the problem, the subject would not require spending time activating a numeric map to answer the problem. The difference in performance is a phenomenon that predicts the NMP, but it has also been observed in various studies. This phenomenon, known as the operator-priming effect (Roussel et al., 2002; Fayol and Thevenot, 2012; Mathieu et al., 2017, 2018), occurs when adults anticipate a “+” or “-” sign before performing a single-digit addition or subtraction problem, and it facilitates their ability to solve the problem. The operator-priming effect aligns with how the NMP determines that the phenomenon of remapping affects subjects doing mental arithmetic. Furthermore, the operator-priming effect is explained by the NMP as a consequence of a process of remapping.
- **Cerebellar activity.** Since the NMP states that the navigational system is key in understanding arithmetical skills, the elements involved in the navigational system must have a role when the human brain carries out calculations. A recent investigation has shown that the cerebellum is involved in the directional modulation of hippocampal place cells Zhang et al. (2023). Given this finding, it should also be involved in the modulation of number cells, and neural activity must appear in the cerebellum when a human being is carrying out arithmetical calculations. In attempting to test this hypothesis against the literature, one can find several studies showing that the cerebellum plays a role in arithmetical calculations (Arsalidou and Taylor, 2011; Peters and De Smedt, 2018; Skagenholt et al., 2021). Thus, cerebellar activity seems to present evidence in favor of the NMP.

4.3.2 Neural activity in mathematical cognitive development

Because the NMP establishes that the navigational system creates a numeric map to understand and carry out simple arithmetical calculations, it implies that different types of evidence should be found in the hippocampus related to mathematical cognitive development in humans. Specifically, we have found the following two types:

- **Higher activity in children than in adults in the hippocampal formation.** The navigational system carries out two different process in learning the structure of one’s environment—learning the states of the environment and learning the transitions between those states—and the hippocampus is implicated in both processes (Liu et al., 2023). According to that fact, if the NMP is true, then a high level of activity should be demonstrated in

the hippocampus during the acquisition of arithmetical skills due to the process of creating a numeric map, since creating a numeric map would involve learning the states and the transitions between those states. Therefore, the activity level in the hippocampus of children creating a numeric map to master arithmetic should be higher than in adults who have already created a numeric map. One investigation has shown that neural activity exists in the hippocampus in adults and in children attempting to answer arithmetical problems, but a higher level of neural activity in the hippocampus is seen in children than in adults while they are resolving the same arithmetical problems (Rivera et al., 2005). That result aligns with the previous prediction deduced from the NMP.

- **Learning arithmetic skills and the functional connectivity between the hippocampus and intraparietal sulcus.** The TCM proposes that the intraparietal sulcus is a key region in arithmetical calculations, and the participation of this region has been confirmed by several studies. If the NMP is correct, the IPS must be functionally connected to the hippocampus. As was mentioned in the previous prediction, the navigational system must create the numeric map. Therefore, the strength of functional connectivity between the hippocampus and intraparietal sulcus must be involved in children’s capacity to learn arithmetic skills. An investigation to study the brain circuits involved in number sense learning has analyzed children aged 7 to 10 years (Chang et al., 2022). The study divided the children by creating two groups. One group completed a four-week training program focused on numerical skills, and the other group did not participate in training. The training had lessons on counting principles, on nonsymbolic and symbolic quantities, and exercises of enumerating and number-ordering. The research compared the groups using functional diffusion and structural MRI scans before and after training. The results revealed the existence of functional connectivity between the left and right hippocampus and the left IPS; furthermore, the experiments showed that the strength of pretraining functional connectivity between the hippocampus and IPS predicted the gains in numerical skills that the children obtained through training. These results match the prediction of the NMP about the creation of a numeric map by the navigational system.

4.3.3 Evidence of the mental representation of numbers and the learning of arithmetic skills

The NMP proposes that mastering arithmetic skills requires the navigational system to create a numeric map. As was shown in Section 4, a numeric map that represents whole or integer numbers must fulfill the condition that the shape of the space must be a specific one, a straight line. Therefore, an immediate prediction of the NMP is that the mental representation of numbers must be a straight line in adults that master arithmetic. The fact that a mental representation of numbers is a line would not be, by itself, proof that the NMP is true because the same mental representation could be produced by another neural system from the navigational system; however, if the requirement was fulfilled that the mental representation of whole and integers numbers was a straight line and there were also connections between that mental representation of numbers and arithmetical skills, then those facts would add support to the previously mentioned evidence—it would show that the NMP is coherent with what is known about the mental representation of whole and integer numbers. The following research related to the mental representation of numbers supports the principle according to the reasoning outlined here.

- **The internal representation of numbers forms a line.** The NMP claims that the navigational system creates a mental representation that allows generating and understanding

arithmetical statements. The mathematical proof presented in this article to show that the navigational system is able to generate and understand arithmetical statements requires the geometrical shape of the navigmap structure to be a straight line. Although the straight-line shape was chosen because the geometric representation of whole and integer numbers is a straight-line, once it is proven that a navigmap with the shape of a straight line allows the understanding and generating of arithmetic statements, that geometric shape assumption emerges as a prediction of the NMP. Thus, if the NMP is correct, the mental representations created by the human brain must have the geometric shape of a straight line.

In examining the literature to evaluate the prediction of a straight line as a mental representation of numbers, a relevant hypothesis, named the mental number line, can be found in the mathematical cognition field. This hypothesis claims that numbers are represented as locations in a mental line (Restle, 1970). Several investigations have found different types of evidence supporting the mental number line hypothesis (Dehaene et al., 1993; Zorzi et al., 2002), indicating that the prediction of the shape of the mental representation of the whole and integer numbers is supported by the literature on the mental representation of numbers in the field of mathematical cognition.

- **The evolution of the shape of the mental representation of numbers.**

It is known that one of the processes the navigational system carries out to create a representation of an environment is learning the relationships between different places in the environment (Liu et al., 2023). The process of learning these relationships involves establishing the direction of and distances between the places in the environment of the spatial representation. If the NMP is correct, then for the development of arithmetical skills the numeric map must be formed by learning not only the numbers but also the distance between the numbers. Thus, a numeric map has the correct distance between two numbers when that distance is equal to the quantity that results from subtracting those two numbers. Since the shape of the space is a one-dimensional line, each number is spatially related only directly with the previous one and the next one.

Several psychological studies have addressed the mental representation of numbers, and three different mental representations have been proposed in the literature: the accumulator model (Gibbon and Church, 1981), the logarithmic model (Dehaene, 1997), and the linear model (Siegler and Opfer, 2003). Robert S. Siegler and John E. Opfer proposed employing two techniques to study the mental representation of numbers: the number-to-position (NP) task and the position-to-number (PN) task (Siegler and Opfer, 2003). Siegler and Opfer examined the performance of adults and second, fourth, and sixth graders on the NP and PN tasks. The results showed that the children knew and used multiple representations of numerical quantity and relied increasingly on a linear representation rather than other representations (intuitive or logarithmic ones). Siegler and Opfer's experiments and results have been replicated (Siegler et al., 2009; Berteletti et al., 2010; Feldman and Berger, 2022), providing support for their results and conclusions. Although some researchers have claimed that the NP task could be unrelated to numerical representation and possibly caused by changes in proportional reasoning (Barth and Paladino, 2011), that claim has been negated because proportional reasoning requires a mental representation of numerical magnitude, so the PN task would also be connected to the mental representation of numbers (Schneider et al., 2018). These findings show that children initially have an inaccurate representation of numerical values, and they acquire linearity by increasing number knowledge step by step.

The condition that a numeric map has the correct distance between two numbers is equiv-

alent to the condition that the mental number line is linear because it involves the mental representation having the correct distance from one number to the previous and the next one. Therefore, the fact that the representation of numbers for the development of arithmetical skills evolves to a linear representation aligns with the prediction that the NMP makes about the evolution of the mental representation of numbers.

- **Correlation between the number line task and predicting arithmetic skill.**

Given that the NMP claims that the navigational system creates a numeric map that allows generating and understanding arithmetical statements and the hypothesis that the shape of the mental number line would be connected with the distances among the locations of the map that represent the numbers in the numeric map, the prediction emerges that the linear shape of a mental number line representation must be correlated with the level of arithmetical skill in children. In other words, children would be able to perform mental arithmetic as correctly as their numeric map is formed, and the shape of a mental number line representation would show how correct the numeric map is that a child has; therefore, the linear shape of a mental number line representation must predict the level of arithmetical skill. Among the research on the number line task, some studies have found that there is correlation between the shape of the mental number line and arithmetic skill. One investigation supported the hypothesis that children’s familiarity with numbers and the shape of the mental number line are related (Berteletti et al., 2015). Another recent investigation has shown that the shape of the mental number line significantly correlates with faster responses in mental arithmetic (Feldman and Berger, 2022). The results of those investigations are consistent with the prediction of the NMP about the correlation between the shape of the mental number line and the arithmetic skill of a human being.

- **Linear numerical training and mathematical competence.**

Related to the previous prediction about the formation of a numeric map and the linear shape of the mental representation of numbers, we can formulate the prediction that if children receive arithmetic training focused on teaching a linear representation of numbers, it must improve arithmetical competence because that training would allow the numeric map to acquire the correct distances between numbers.

Studies have also researched whether training with linear numerical board games can improve mathematical competence in children. The results indicate that children who play linear numerical board games improve their arithmetical competence (Ramani and Siegler, 2008; Whyte and Bull, 2008), whereas training with circular board games does not improve arithmetical competence (Siegler and Ramani, 2009). Therefore, the prediction that linear numerical training improves mathematical competence because of the formation of the numeric map is in line with the results from studies that have addressed training with linear numerical aspects.

4.3.4 Pathologies that affect hippocampal formation

The last type of evidence in support of the NMP is related to pathologies that affect the navigational system. Given that the NMP connects the navigational system with arithmetical abilities, one kind of prediction and test that emerges is related to situations in which damage to the navigational system produces deficits in arithmetical abilities. If the NMP is correct, an impairment in an individual’s navigational skills will be accompanied by impairment in the understanding and generation of arithmetical statements. In this case, any pathology involving damage to the hippocampal formation or any other region involved in mental navigation must affect arithmetical skills.

- **Alzheimer’s disease and arithmetical skills.** A feature of Alzheimer’s disease (AD) is that the first anatomical structure damaged by the condition is the hippocampus (Boutet et al., 2014; Rao et al., 2022), meaning that the navigational system is affected early on (Coughlan et al., 2018). It is known that navigation abilities are damaged in people with AD, and according to the NMP, AD should cause a deficit in arithmetical calculations because the disease affects the hippocampal formation. Thus, a prediction of the NMP is that patients with AD suffer dyscalculia early.

Starting with that prediction, we searched the literature for studies devoted to analyzing the relationship between AD and calculation abilities, and we found several studies analyzing this issue (Rosselli et al., 1998; Mantovan et al., 1999; Carlomagno et al., 1999; Martin et al., 2003; Arnaud et al., 2008). These various investigations have consistently indicated that patients with AD suffer a loss of arithmetical abilities. Although AD causes extensive damage throughout the brain and it could be argued that the deficit might not be generated by damage to the navigational system, some of the previous studies that specifically addressed arithmetical skills in the early stages of AD found that AD patients experience dyscalculia (Carlomagno et al., 1999; Martin et al., 2003). Integrating the facts mentioned, it becomes clear that AD presents an initial impairment in the navigational system in the early stages of the disease accompanied by impairment in understanding and generating arithmetical statements. Thus, the pathology of AD matches the prediction of the NMP.

- **Fragile X syndrome and dyscalculia.** Fragile X syndrome (FXS) is a genetic disorder caused by transcriptional silencing of the Fragile X Mental Retardation 1 gene, producing the loss of Fragile X Messenger Ribonucleoprotein (FMRP). FXS affects different areas of the brain, and one structure that is significantly impacted by the loss of FMRP is the hippocampal formation (Leontiadis et al., 2024; Bostrom et al., 2016). In particular, it is known that FMRP regulates heterosynaptic plasticity in the hippocampus (Connor et al., 2011). Consistently with the previous facts, it has also been determined that humans affected by FSX suffer impairment of their spatial processing (MacLeod et al., 2010). Consistent with the discoveries previously mentioned, it has also been determined that humans affected by FSX suffer impairments in spatial processing (MacLeod et al., 2010). Considering the previous facts and the NMP, we derive the prediction that patients with FXS should suffer dyscalculia. We searched the literature for studies devoted to analyzing the relationship between FXS and calculation abilities, and we found studies showing a relationship between FXS and mathematical learning disabilities (Murphy, 2009). Thus, FXS is in accordance with the prediction of the NMP.
- **Dyscalculia.** In research on dyscalculia in children, structural deficits in the hippocampus and entorhinal cortex have been found (Rykhlevskaia et al., 2009). These two regions are key structures in the navigational system in mammals. According to the NMP, deficits in the hippocampus and entorhinal cortex must affect the understanding of arithmetic because the damage would prevent the formation of the numeric map and its use. Thus, the deficits found in hippocampal structures of children with dyscalculia match the prediction of the NMP.
- **Acalculia.** Damage in the subcortical structures of the navigational system must also produce a deficit in arithmetical calculations. Dehaene and Cohen described a patient, BOO, who suffered a capsulo-lenticular hemorrhage (Dehaene and Cohen, 1997). The CT scan showed that BOO had a hypodense slit that affected the left lenticular nucleus, head of the caudate, internal capsule, and insula. BOO also suffered a severe calculation deficit. For example, BOO was not able to count backward by three starting with 50. Investigation into the

dorsal striatum has shown that the nucleus caudate plays a key role in flexible navigation (Gahnstrom and Spiers, 2020). Also, another study has noted that the insula is involved in navigation (Zwergal et al., 2016). Therefore, the damage BOO experienced in the nucleus caudate and insula and the deficit in calculation are in agreement with the prediction of the NMP that damage to elements of the navigational system produces a deficit in arithmetical calculation.

5 Discussion

In the previous section, we presented the NMP and showed how, from a mathematical point of view, the NMP hypothesis can be key to solving the SGPNC, and we presented different neuroscientific and psychological facts in agreement with the NMP. Below, we discuss how the NMP is related to the previously developed assumptions and concepts of numerical cognition of number sense and the memory retrieval hypothesis, the structure of spatial knowledge, and how the NMP can be tested. Many other topics could be discussed, but because of space limitations, in this paper we focus on the topics mentioned, and the discussion of other issues impacted by the NMP will be deferred to future articles.

5.1 Numeric map principle and number sense

The concept of a number is an abstraction from the cardinality or numerosity of a group of objects, but we must be aware that a number is different from the quantity of objects that a group of objects contains because a number does not require referencing any group of objects. Likewise, addition and subtraction are abstractions of grouping and removing objects from groups of objects, respectively; however, the operations of addition and subtraction with numbers must be distinguished from the actions of grouping and removing objects because arithmetic operations do not require referencing any groups of objects. These important differences lie in the fact that a number has an entity by itself in the human mind. For example, if a human being thinks of 7, it is an entity by itself that is not bound to a group of seven apples or seven chairs nor any other set of objects that has seven objects. The fact that a number has an entity by itself has fascinated great minds over time, resulting in the following question: How can a number have an entity by itself? It has led to philosophical views such as Platonism (Gray, 2008), but neuroscience cannot accept that kind of answer, and it aspires to achieve an explanation that avoids mystical elements.

One proposed answer is number sense (Dehaene, 1997). Neuroscience research has shown that innate mechanisms exist to determine the quantities of objects in the environment, which was enunciated in the hypothesis of number sense (Nieder, 2016). However, number sense is not able to resolve the SGPNC, as we have explained. Given that data support the existence of the number sense in the human brain, it seems that we require another piece to complete the puzzle. We propose that the NMP could be this piece of the puzzle. The NMP proposes that the navigational system creates a mental construct, the numeric map, that allows grounding symbols of numbers and operations. This answers how a number can have an entity by itself, since the numeric map is a structure that determines how one of its elements is related to the rest of the elements contained in it. This is a key feature of numbers. The identity of a number does not depend only on itself but on how that number is related to the rest of the numbers. For example, the number 7 is defined as an entity, but it is only part of its meaning; all its meaning involves how it is specifically related to all the other numbers, since $7 + 1$ must be 8 and $7 - 1$ must be 6; if the results of those operations were different, 7 would not denote the number we know by that symbol.

Given that key feature, it is interesting to note that the navigational system creates spatial

representations that contain entities that are related among them. A cognitive map represents an environment, and an environment consists of places, and a place is not an entity by itself, but its complete meaning implies establishing the distance and paths among the place and the rest of places of the environment. Therefore, number sense and the NMP would be two pieces of the puzzle named SGPNC, but the NMP is not the last piece of the puzzle — mathematical cognition is a very wide and complex skill, but if it is correct, it will be a breakthrough towards solving the SGPNC.

5.2 The numeric map principle versus the memory retrieval hypothesis

The hypothesis that mental arithmetic consists of retrieving simple arithmetic facts was first proposed by John Parkman, who, based on experiments in which the reaction time of subjects performing arithmetic was measured, proposed that simple addition and multiplication are carried out by the same process, which involves a memory retrieval operation (Parkman, 1972). Later, also on the basis of experiments measuring reaction time, Mark Ashcraft and John Battaglia proposed that adults retrieve the answers to simple calculation problems from memory (e.g., $3 + 4$). They formulated the specific hypothesis that adults store simple addition problems in a network representation and retrieve them by means of a spreading-activation search (Ashcraft and Battaglia, 1978). McCloskey et al. (1991b) analyzed the mental models of retrieving arithmetic facts using subjects with fact retrieval deficits. Dehaene and Cohen, according to the analysis of two acalculic patients, suggested that there is a double dissociation in numerical processing in which one of the routes is involved in retrieving and storing verbal arithmetic facts (Dehaene and Cohen, 1997).

Although the TCM has not taken into account the activity in the hippocampal formation, many studies have observed hippocampal activity in human subjects doing mental arithmetic (Rivera et al., 2005; Supekar et al., 2013; Qin et al., 2014; Moeller et al., 2015; Rosenberg-Lee et al., 2015; Menon, 2016; Kuhl et al., 2020; Menon and Chang, 2021; Das and Menon, 2022). That neural activity has been interpreted according to the memory retrieval hypothesis (or semantic memory hypothesis). The explanation of the memory retrieval hypothesis was adopted by Menon and colleagues to explain the hippocampal activity observed in their investigations. The memory retrieval hypothesis is based on the fact that the structures of the medial temporal lobe are considered the anatomical support of declarative memory (Squire et al., 2004). Declarative memory is divided into episodic and semantic memory, the latter of which specifically refers to the ability to remember facts. In addition, the retrieving hypothesis has been adopted by other scientists to explain their observations of hippocampal activity during mental arithmetic (Klein et al., 2016; Bloechle et al., 2016). Overall, the scientific community has largely accepted the memory retrieval hypothesis as the explanation for interpreting the neural activity observed in the hippocampus (Smaczny et al., 2023; Suárez-Pellicioni et al., 2022; Peters and De Smedt, 2018; Moeller et al., 2015). According to this hypothesis, the hippocampal activity observed in children has been associated with the acquisition of retrieval-based solution strategies, while in adults hippocampal-parietal connectivity has been associated with the retrieval of arithmetic facts (Moeller et al., 2015). Thus, the current dogma is that the role of the hippocampus during mental arithmetic is related to declarative memory (or more specifically to semantic memory).

In subsection 4.3, we presented facts that support the NMP interpretation and are in agreement with the predictions derived from the NMP. However, several of those facts have been interpreted under the memory retrieval hypothesis by the researchers that carried out the investigations. Given that the memory retrieval hypothesis has been the interpretation used until now to explain the neural activity in the hippocampal formation for mental arithmetic, it is necessary to confront one hypothesis with the other. Therefore, we must discuss what the NMP brings to the understanding of arithmetical skills compared with the memory retrieval hypothesis.

Firstly, it is necessary to understand more deeply the framework in which the retrieving hypothesis emerges. Parkman (1972), and later Ashcraft and Battaglia (1978), proposed the memory retrieval hypothesis because their views about mental arithmetic were that the human brain retrieves arithmetical facts and combines them using algorithms adequate for carrying out arithmetical calculations. This view is based on the fact that the traditional rote learning of addition and multiplication is based on memorizing tables and using algorithms for calculations with numbers of two or more digits.

At this point a question emerges: is the retrieving hypothesis sufficient for explaining how the human brain has generated arithmetic? Assuming that mental arithmetic consists of a process of retrieving arithmetical facts, applying the rules of an algorithm creates an important gap because that framework cannot answer how those arithmetical facts were generated by humans. Someone can learn a mathematical fact without understanding its meaning. For example, a child not trained in arithmetical skills can learn $7 + 2 = 9$ as a sequence of words. However, that verbal fact by itself lacks any arithmetical meaning since the child could learn $7 + 2 = 6$.

The semantic gap pointed out shows that, although it is true that the human brain memorizes addition and multiplication tables, it does not imply that mental arithmetic can be fully explained within that framework. The criticism expressed about the memory retrieval hypothesis is not denying that memory retrieval plays an important role in long calculations. In fact, we are aware that in most educational systems, students learn multiplication tables as verbal facts using a multiplication algorithm, column multiplication, that allows multiplying two or more-digit numbers by another number of two or more digits. Therefore, arithmetical facts are learned, but before a mathematical fact can be learned it must be previously established. Therefore, while the human brain carries out the retrieval of arithmetical facts, the memory retrieval hypothesis has two weaknesses if one wants to use it to explain all mental arithmetic: 1) a verbal arithmetic fact does not have meaning because the hypothesis reduces all mental arithmetic to merely recovering facts and applying rules to them, and 2) there is no room for a process of calculation that allows for determining whether an arithmetical statement is true or false. Those weaknesses lead to the deduction that mental arithmetic cannot be completely explained based on retrieving facts and using rewritten rules to perform complex arithmetic calculations; therefore, it is necessary to add a mechanism that explains how the human brain generates arithmetical facts and validates them. For some time, it has been thought that basic arithmetical facts could be generated by number sense (Dehaene, 1997). However, as we have already discussed, it does not resolve the SGPNC even though it is accepted that there is an innate number sense (the ANS). In fact, number sense explains only the skill of counting objects, since an arithmetical fact cannot be observed by the senses because numbers are not physical objects that exist in a natural environment. This is where the NMP comes into play. The NMP answers the question of how arithmetical statements are generated and understood, proposing that the human brain uses the navigational system. The NMP does not claim that the navigational system is the only way in which humans carry out arithmetic calculations — in fact, we know that while children learn arithmetic they go through different stages in which they use different strategies (e.g., counting with the fingers (Frey et al., 2024)) — but what it does propose is that the navigational system provides the mental mechanism capable of generating simple arithmetical facts and validating them. Thus, the activity registered in the hippocampus that has been interpreted as the learning of mathematical facts has a different interpretation under the NMP. The new interpretation provides a new explanation of the hippocampal activity observed based on the investigations of the navigational system. In this case, the high level of activity in the hippocampus observed in children when they are learning arithmetic would be due to the navigational system generating a numeric map, since it has been observed that learning an environment to generate a representation to navigate in it involves generating activity in the

hippocampus (Shin et al., 2019).

The fact that offers more support to the NMP as an explanation of hippocampal activity over the memory retrieval hypothesis is the inactivity of the hippocampus when a subject performs multiplication. The reasoning is the following:

The memory retrieval hypothesis has been used by different authors to explain the differences that they found in the hippocampal activity in experiments with addition and subtraction De Smedt et al. (2011); Cho et al. (2012). The experiments showed higher activity for addition than for subtraction, and this fact was interpreted by the authors to be the result of addition being retrieved, unlike what happened in subtraction. For example, when Cho et al. (2012) analyzed their results, they explained that the subtractions “are less well rehearsed and more difficult to memorize because problems are not commutative” (Cho et al., 2012, p. 1850). According to the memory retrieval hypothesis, hippocampal activity is related to retrieving arithmetic facts, and it should therefore also be observed in retrieving simple multiplication facts — as children, people memorize multiplication tables and later carry out all multiplication by retrieving those memorized facts. Also, if the hippocampus is damaged, people are unable to retrieve simple multiplication facts. However, these predictions are contradicted by experimental studies. Mathieu et al. (2017) found that the hippocampus was not active in a task in which subjects were required to multiply. Furthermore, an investigation in patients with Alzheimer’s disease, who had severely damaged hippocampuses in comparison with healthy controls, reported that 13 of 16 patients retrieved overlearned arithmetical facts (i.e. multiplication tables) in the average range of standardised norms (Delazer et al., 2019). These findings indicate that the hippocampus is not critically involved in retrieving overlearned arithmetic facts.

Since the only explanation available to researchers to date to explain the hippocampal activity that appears while subjects perform mental arithmetic has been the memory retrieval hypothesis, this explanation has continued to be adopted by researchers i.e. Tejero and Macizo (2020). However, investigations about multiplication facts have shown that the hippocampus does not play any role in retrieving them (Mathieu et al., 2017; Delazer et al., 2019). Regardless of whether the NMP is correct or not, how the memory retrieval hypothesis has been used to interpret the results from some experiments on simple addition is contradictory. Using the principle of Occam’s razor, we should not choose as an explanation a theory that multiplies entities by separating the storing and retrieving of addition and multiplication facts without a good argument to justify it. A lack of strong justification in the explanation for multiplying the entities indicates that it is necessary to consider the existence of an alternative explanation that does not multiply the entities for the same type of process.

Now, we are going to do the opposite exercise — we are going to address a refutation of the NMP. If the NMP is correct, then activity in the hippocampus must be observed in subjects solving addition and subtraction problems. Therefore, one could argue that the NMP could be refuted because De Smedt et al. (2011) found a greater hippocampal response in children than in adults solving addition problems but not when they were solving subtraction problems. However, two counterarguments exist for rejecting the argument to refute the NMP. The first counterargument is that De Smedt et al. (2011) did not find the hippocampus to be inactive but less active in subtraction than in addition. The second counterargument, which reinforces the previous one, is that recent research registering neural activity with electrodes in adults has identified activity in the hippocampus in both addition and subtraction operations (Kutter et al., 2022). Therefore, the results of De Smedt et al. (2011) do not reject the NMP, and the reason for less activity could be related to the children’s mental arithmetic stage or the methodology of the experiments.

At this point it is interesting to note that the NMP distinguishes between giving meaning to a multiplication fact and retrieving a multiplication fact. The process of how the navigation system

can carry out multiplication or division shown in Subsection 4.1.8 would allow understanding multiplication and division statements. However, it is a costly process in terms of time and energy; a much less costly process would exist that allows retrieving multiplication and division facts. The easier process would be an associative memory process, which would explain why the human brain can retrieve multiplication facts without hippocampal involvement, as has been demonstrated in various studies (Mathieu et al., 2017; Delazer et al., 2019). That associative memory process could also be used by the human brain to retrieve addition and subtraction facts for those addition and subtraction facts that are overlearned. Thus, the NMP could explain some pathologies observed in patients that have their comprehension skills affected but not their ability to recover simple mathematical facts since there is a dissociation between both processes.

The most important difference between the memory retrieval hypothesis and the NMP is the consideration that each one gives to the facts. While the memory retrieval hypothesis considers each arithmetic fact an independent entity that is merely a sequence of words, the NMP proposes that simple arithmetic facts cannot be independent entities because the numeric map is a structure that arises from how they relate to each other. Thus, a numeric map would allow one to retrieve simple arithmetical facts since it stores in its own structure how small numbers are related among them according to arithmetical operations; however, one must be aware that it is a much more complex concept than merely memorizing facts. In the field of psychology, the classification of types of memory is a substantial topic of discussion (Tulving, 2007; Renoult and Rugg, 2020). Thus, if the NMP is correct, we should distinguish between arithmetic facts that can be retrieved from the numeric map and arithmetic facts that are retrieved from the memories that store the facts as independent entities.

We think that, independent of which of the hypotheses is correct, the formulation of the NMP brings about a new hypothesis for discussing data from experiments, which would benefit research on mathematical cognition. The search to test each hypothesis will lead us to better understanding the system through new experiments designed to reveal the differences between both hypotheses or even to discover unknown phenomena that require the development of more complex theories.

5.3 The cognitive map and the numeric map

Regarding debates in the field of psychology in the first half of the 20th century about behavior, Tolman defended the idea that not all compartments could be explained by the stimulus-response structure. His research with rats led him to propose that map-like structures were involved in the generation of navigational behavior (Tolman, 1948). Thus, he introduced the concept of cognitive maps for problem-solving and inference navigation allowing purposive behavior in animals and men. The cognitive map hypothesis proposes that the brain builds a unified representation of the spatial environment to support memory and guide future action (Epstein et al., 2017). After the discovery of place cells by O’Keefe and Dostrovsky (O’Keefe and Dostrovsky, 1971), O’Keefe and Nadel wrote the now famous book, *The Hippocampus as a Cognitive Map*, that provided a neural substrate to Tolman’s idea of a cognitive map (O’Keefe and Nadel, 1978).

Tolman was using the word “cognitive” to qualify the map as a spatial mental representation of the environment against the doctrine of behaviorism in which only stimulus-response structures existed in the brain. Over the last few years, it has been proposed that the hippocampus could generate other mental representations that the human brain would handle as maps. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, in addition to being involved in representing the locations that exist in an environment and the spatial relations among them, the navigational system and the hippocampal formation have only been implicated in temporal representation (Hassabis and Maguire, 2007), music representation (Teki et al., 2012), social roles (Kong et al., 2023), and conceptual spaces

(Viganò et al., 2021). However, the proposal that the navigational system creates a map to allow the human brain to generate and understand arithmetic statements has not yet been proposed.

Until now, only Huber et al. (2016) have proposed that associations exist between number and space according to the spatial-numerical association of response codes (SNARC) effect, and Mathieu and his collaborators have conducted experiments in which spatial mechanisms were observed (Mathieu et al., 2017) in agreement with Huber et al. (2016). However, those claims have been explained in regard to the mental number line proposed by Dehaene and collaborators that proposed it was localized in cortical areas (Dehaene et al., 1993; Izard and Dehaene, 2008). Thus, they are not able to explain why the hippocampus is related to some arithmetic operators and not others. In such an approach, the hippocampus has only been considered a secondary mechanism that is used in some cases. In contrast with that view, the NMP claims that the navigational system has a principal role in mastering arithmetic skills because it would create a map specifically for the numbers that allow it to generate and understand arithmetic facts. The NMP explains from a neuroscientific point of view that addition is a fundamental operation, unlike multiplication; there is a specific circuit for addition, whereas multiplication can be reduced to addition and would be grounded using the addition circuit. Due to that difference, there must be a mechanism to generate additional facts, but multiplication facts would be generated using the addition mechanism and stored. This offers an explanation as to why the addition symbol is linked to hippocampal activity but the multiplication symbol is not; there is no multiplicative mechanism, and the multiplication symbol is only linked to retrieving multiplicative facts.

It is interesting to note that the NMP, despite not using the word cognitive, formulates a hypothesis about a cognitive process that is much more abstract than the process of navigation considered in the cognitive map. While the entities of the cognitive map represent physical locations of an environment, there is no physical entity that can be identified with a number. Thus, the concept of a numeric map goes further than the concept of a cognitive map — a cognitive map is a mental representation, whereas a numeric map is not a mental representation but a mental construction because it is not representing anything that exists in the physical world.

5.4 The numeric map principle, metric cognitive map hypothesis, and cognitive graph hypothesis

In the field of navigation, a topic of discussion is whether the mental representation of an environment in the mammalian brain uses an innate Euclidean metric (Gallistel, 1990; McNaughton et al., 2006) or the metric cognitive map hypothesis, or whether there is no Euclidean metric in the brain. The proposal that the navigational system does not have an innate Euclidean metric is called the cognitive graph hypothesis (Warren, 2019). This hypothesis proposes that the mammalian brain, and specifically the human brain, uses a mental structure similar to a labelled graph to describe the navigational space of an environment. While the metric cognitive map better explains how an animal performs flexible navigation, the cognitive graph better explains how spatial knowledge of the environment is acquired (Ericson and Warren, 2020). Although both hypotheses were initially presented as two hypotheses that exclude each other (Warren et al., 2017), it was later proposed that both mechanisms could coexist in the human brain (Peer, 2020).

In this paper we do not discuss the specific structure of spatial knowledge used by the navigational system, but the question obviously affects the NMP. Specifically, a reader could wonder whether it would affect the NMP if the graph hypothesis was correct and there was no metric cognitive map. The answer is that it would not affect the NMP because the numeric map could also be built as a labelled graph. The reason is that a numeric line of whole numbers is a one-dimensional space, and that one-dimensional space can be described perfectly by a labelled graph in which

each node represents a whole number and the edges are marked with the distance between both nodes and the angle. The labelled graph that forms the numeric map is isomorphic to a Euclidean one-dimensional space because it must fulfill the three following conditions:

- Each location of the map corresponds to a node of the graph and the reverse.
- The angles between two neighboring nodes must be 0 degrees with its successor and 180 degrees with its predecessor.
- The distance between two nodes is a multiple of the length between the node that represents 0 and the node that represents 1. Specifically, the value of the multiple is the length between the node that represents 0 and the node that represents 1 multiplied by the result of the subtraction of the number associated with the node that represents the smallest number from the number associated with the node that represents the largest number. Mathematically, the length assigned to each edge is as follows:

$$length(n_x, n_y) = \begin{cases} length(n_0, n_1) * (x - y) & , \text{ if } x > y \\ length(n_0, n_1) * (y - x) & , \text{ if } x < y \\ 0 & , \text{ if } x = y \end{cases}$$

5.5 Testing and open questions of the numeric map principle

In subsection 4.3, we presented some predictions derived from the NMP. However, it seems logical for readers to ask how the NMP can be tested and whether it is really a mechanism that the human brain uses for arithmetical skills. The answer to this question lies in the fact that the NMP proposes that the navigational system is in charge of grounding arithmetical symbols and performing simple arithmetical operations, since the same circuits would be carried out in both tasks. Therefore, the brain activity registered in human beings doing mental navigation in an environment whose shape is a straight line and those doing arithmetical operations (not retrieving a memorized value) should be the same in the hippocampal formation. Currently, some experiments have been carried out to register the activity of human beings during navigation (Chrastil et al., 2022). Therefore, an experiment to test the NMP would register the activity of subjects navigating and doing simple addition and subtraction. After registering both neural activities, it will be necessary to compare them. If the NMP is correct, simple mental arithmetic should generate the same kind of activity as navigation.

Another important issue in testing the NMP is the kind of technology used to observe the neural activity of subjects doing mental arithmetic. This relates to an issue that the reader could be pondering: why the hippocampal formation has not appeared in different investigations about mental arithmetic (Fehr et al., 2007). The answer might be in the temporal resolution of fMRI. In fMRI, the repetition time, a parameter that determines how long it takes a measure to be repeated in the same location, is 2000 ms in many investigations. According to the NMP, the mental arithmetic of simple calculations is carried out by the replay process, which is fast. The neural activity that happens in the hippocampus formation lasts less than 2000 ms. Although fMRI is an important technology in investigating some elements of the networks involved in arithmetical skills, it is limited if we want to go further. In addition, if we want to better understand the mathematical skills of humans, we require technologies that record from single neurons or with a better temporal resolution. Magnetocardiography has a better temporal resolution than fMRI, but testing the NMP requires examining subcortical structures and advanced mathematical tools.

One open question that emerges in the event that the NMP is correct is how accurate the navigmap is as a mathematical description of the mental representations that the navigational

system creates of an environment and the operations that can be carried out there. The navigmap mathematically formalizes a number of features that have been discovered by studying the navigational system, but there are other features that could play an important role that have not been incorporated in the definition of the navigmap. Research and discoveries about the human navigational system could help determine how correct the mathematical definition of the navigmap is in describing the functioning and elements used by the navigational system. The following is an example. If the human brain uses the navigational system to execute a simple mental addition or subtraction operation and obtain the result, then the human brain would be using the same mechanism that it uses to determine where one will arrive if one travels a length (or at a certain speed for an amount of time) in one direction. Preliminarily, we can state that there will be two options to investigate as solutions: a) generating the final position or b) traveling the path.

6 Summary and conclusions

Achieving a deep understanding of human mathematical skills involves knowing how neuronal activity generates mathematical abilities in the human brain. Currently, a large gap exists in this research area. Two of the main problems are the SGPNC and how the human brain carries out arithmetical operations. Regarding these topics, the research presented in this article focuses on finding a neuronal system that explains how the human brain is able to understand and master the concepts involved in arithmetic, leading us to present a new hypothesis, the numeric map principle (NMP).

The starting hypothesis has been that the navigational system, located mainly in the hippocampal formation, is involved in how the human brain is able to generate, understand, and master the concepts involved in arithmetic. This hypothesis connects two areas of research in neuroscience that were previously disconnected: navigation and numerical processing. The article has first presented a review of findings from each of these two areas. Regarding number processing, many of the models developed have focused on explaining neural codes to represent numbers. Among these models, the most accepted is the TCM. Although the TCM allows understanding different aspects of numerical cognition related to the codes for representing numerical information, it lacks an explanation for how the human brain carries out arithmetic operations. Regarding the SGPNC, one of the proposals for solving this issue is the ANS hypothesis. However, despite being considered a promising hypothesis to the SGPNC, after years of research, the scientific community has dismissed the idea that the ANS is the basis for solving the SGPNC.

Given the lack of a clear line of research to resolve the SGPNC and understanding of how the human brain performs arithmetical calculations, we have conducted, as part of this research, a search for the conditions that must be fulfilled by a neural system that is able to ground arithmetical symbols. Specifically, three conditions have been inferred from different facts already known about mental arithmetic, and we present them in this article. The first two conditions involve how mental representations should be generated and handled. Both conditions are fulfilled by the navigational system. The third condition establishes that a neural system must be powerful enough to represent numbers and arithmetic operations; in other words, it must generate and host a mental representation of the mathematical structure associated to the arithmetic. This last condition is key to considering it plausible that the navigational system plays a role in the numeral processing performed by the human brain.

Addressing whether the navigational system fulfills the third condition requires a mathematical approach. Specifically, the condition is expressed using the framework of universal algebra. The third condition expresses mathematically the existence of an isomorphism between internal representations and arithmetical structures. To prove the existence of an isomorphism, we define a new kind of

mathematical structure, named *navimap*, which formalizes the features observed in research on the navigational system in mammals. We demonstrate that an isomorphism can be defined between a *navimap* of a one-dimensional space and a substructure of the ring of integers. The existence of the mentioned isomorphism shows that it is plausible that human beings use the navigational system to generate and understand arithmetic knowledge.

After showing that the navigational system fulfills these three conditions, we have discussed the starting hypothesis as a principle for interpreting neural activity to understand how the human brain is able to generate and understand arithmetic knowledge, and we have formulated the NMP. The NMP dictates that the human brain creates an internal map, called the *numeric map*. Each location represents a different number, the different types of displacements are interpreted as arithmetic operators, and a movement from one location to another through the *numeric map* is an arithmetical calculation. Thus, the navigational system could allow the human brain to create and host internal representations that are copies of the mathematical structures that contain arithmetic, which would allow arithmetical symbol grounding. It is interesting to note that there are multiple open questions about the mechanisms the brain uses to navigate, and if the NMP is confirmed, finding answers to those questions will help in understanding how the human brain has mathematical abilities.

The NMP provides an interpretation of the neural activity registered in the hippocampal formation and extrahippocampal regions when humans perform basic arithmetic operations, such as addition and subtraction. According to this interpretation, we have discussed four kinds of evidence supporting the NMP that we found in the literature. The first is the similarity between the neuronal activity registered for number processing in basic neuroscience research and the neural activity registered for navigation. The second involves the anatomical results of studies on individual differences in mathematical cognitive development. The third is the similarity with specific techniques to facilitate the learning of arithmetic skills. The last kind of evidence that has been presented is the existence of findings regarding pathologies related to the hippocampal formation and extrahippocampal regions that affect arithmetical skills.

After providing evidence that supports the NMP, we have discussed various topics related to the NMP and the interpretations it proposes. The first issue was the difference between the semantic memory hypothesis for interpreting hippocampal activity and the new view proposed by the NMP. The second issue was the difference between arithmetic and numerical magnitude and what the NMP brings to the SGPNC in comparison with number sense and the ANS. The third issue was what role the NMP plays in the mathematical cognitive development. The fourth issue was how the mechanisms of arithmetical skills have appeared in the human brain. The fifth issue was the difference between the concepts of cognitive and *numeric maps*. The last issue involved predictions derived from the NMP and how the *numeric map* can be tested.

In summary, we present here the NMP, a principle that explains how the human brain can generate and understand arithmetical knowledge and that interprets the activity observed in neuronal circuits of the hippocampal formation in humans during arithmetical calculation. This new view that the NMP provides creates a framework that allows integrating neuroscientific facts that, until now, lacked a theoretical framework in which to connect them. The NMP also explains psychological facts about mathematical cognitive development. We encourage the scientific community to test the NMP because we consider it to be a starting point for a new line of research relevant to neuroscience, neuropsychology, computational cognition, and artificial intelligence. If the NMP is confirmed, it will serve as a *rosetta stone* that explains the meaning of neuronal activity associated with arithmetical calculations by translating from the navigational system to number processing. This means that an important step in solving the SGPNC will have been taken. We also hope that the new ideas related to answering the SGPNC, the NMP, and the open questions

presented in this article will stimulate further research on number processing and lead to a deeper understanding of how humans possess complex cognitive capacities.

APPENDIX A: Concepts of universal algebra and model theory

Here, we briefly introduce the concepts of mathematical structure, signature, formal language, alphabet, assignation, theory, and model.

A mathematical structure \mathfrak{A} is a triad of three sets $\mathfrak{A} = \langle \{\mathbf{A}_i\}, \{\mathbf{f}_k\}, \{\mathbf{R}_l\} \rangle$ where each \mathbf{A}_i is a sort, each \mathbf{f}_k is a function, and each \mathbf{R}_l is a relation. The domain and codomain of each function \mathbf{f}_k are sorts \mathbf{A}_i or a Cartesian product of them. Each \mathbf{R}_l is a subset of a finite Cartesian product of sorts of the mathematical structure. A mathematical structure that does not have any relation and has one or more functions is named algebra. The mathematical structures studied in arithmetic usually have only one sort, which is a set of numbers (e.g., whole numbers, integers, rational numbers, real numbers).

Each mathematical structure has an associated signature (also named type). Different formalisms can be found in different textbooks to describe the signature of a mathematical structure, but all are equivalents. In this case, we present the most general formalism for a signature. Signature τ has three sets $\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}$ and a function μ . The set \mathcal{S} is an index set where each element identifies one and only one sort. The sets \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{R} contain function symbols and relation symbols, respectively. \mathcal{F} has as many elements as the mathematical structure has functions, and \mathcal{R} has as many elements as the mathematical structure has relations. In this formalization of the signature, there is no set of constant symbols because they are formalized as 0-ary functions. The function μ describes on which sorts are defined functions and relations. It is defined as follows:

$$\mu : \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{R} \longrightarrow \mathcal{S}_\omega$$

where \mathcal{S}_ω is the set of all the finite sequences of indexes associated with the set of sorts, \mathcal{S} .

Given signature τ , it is possible to build a formal language $L(\tau)$. $L(\tau)$ is adequate to express statements for any mathematical structure \mathfrak{A} whose signature is τ . The alphabet of $L(\tau)$, Σ , contains the non-logical symbols that τ has, and also logical symbols and auxiliary symbols. $L(\tau)$ is a subset of Σ^* where Σ^* is the set of all the finite strings generated using Σ . Each element of $L(\tau)$ is named formula. A formula without free variables is denominated sentence.

An assignation is a function that associates variables of the language $L(\tau)$ with elements of the sorts of \mathfrak{A} and non-logical symbols of $L(\tau)$ with functions and relations of \mathfrak{A} . Given an assignation, a formula is satisfiable when the translation of the formula using the assignation matches that of the mathematical structure.

Given an assignation, a set of sentences, T , is a theory of \mathfrak{A} if each sentence of T is satisfiable in \mathfrak{A} . \mathfrak{A} is a model of T , if all the sentences of T are satisfiable by \mathfrak{A} .

APPENDIX B: Commutativity and associativity of $merge^+$

There are two reasonably natural ways of proving the commutativity and associativity of $merge^+$. The first is by induction. The second is using the indexes that are used to denote the elements of \mathbf{L} and \mathbf{P} . The second technique is based on the fact that the indexes are the elements of whole numbers, \mathbb{N}_0 , and the commutativity and associativity are well known properties of the addition operation, $+$, on \mathbb{N}_0 . The proof using the indexes is simpler than the proof by induction. For that

reason, the proofs of commutativity and associativity that are presented below use indexes.

Lemma 6.1. *merge⁺ is commutative.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
+(x, y) &= +(y, x) \\
\text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(x, y)) &= \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(y, x)) \\
\text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(x, y)) &= \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(y, x)) \\
\text{merge}^+(\mathbf{l}_x, \mathbf{l}_y) &= \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{l}_y, \mathbf{l}_x) \\
\mathbf{l}_{x+y} &= \mathbf{l}_{y+x} \\
\mathbf{l}_{x+y} &= \mathbf{l}_{x+y}
\end{aligned}$$

QED

This proves that *merge⁺* is commutative and the addition operation, +, is equivalent to *merge⁺*.

Lemma 6.2. *merge⁺ is associative.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
+((x, y), z) &= +(x, +(y, z)) \\
\text{merge}^+(\text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(x, y)), \mathbf{h}(z)) &= \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(x), \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(y, z))) \\
\text{merge}^+(\text{mix}^+(\mathbf{h}(x, y)), \mathbf{h}(z)) &= \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(x), (\text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(y, z)))) \\
\text{merge}^+(\text{merge}^+(\mathbf{l}_x, \mathbf{l}_y), \mathbf{h}(z)) &= \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(x), \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{l}_y, \mathbf{l}_z)) \\
\text{merge}^+(\mathbf{l}_{x+y}, \mathbf{h}(z)) &= \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{h}(x), \mathbf{l}_{y+z}) \\
\text{merge}^+(\mathbf{l}_{x+y}, \mathbf{l}_z) &= \text{merge}^+(\mathbf{l}_x, \mathbf{l}_{y+z}) \\
\mathbf{l}_{x+y+z} &= \mathbf{l}_{x+y+z}
\end{aligned}$$

QED

This proves that *merge⁺* is associative and the addition operation, +, is equivalent to *merge⁺*.

Acknowledgments

I want to thank Dr. Juan Marcos Alarcon for allowing me to assist in his course Neuronal Systems at SUNY Downstate University Health Sciences during my stay there. He created the perfect environment to stimulate my thoughts and develop the core of the ideas presented here, and he read this paper and identified typos and unclear paragraphs. I want to thank Dr. John Kubie for his lectures at Downstate University Health Sciences about the navigational system. Due to his explanations, I focused my attention on the navigation system. I also want to thank Dr. Kubie for his comments during our meetings at SUNY Downstate Health Sciences University because they prompted me to study the navigation system deeply. I am also grateful to Lori-Ann Tuscan for assisting with language editing. Finally, I want to thank the Research Executive Agency for its financial support because without it, this research never would have been possible.

Funding Information

The research presented here has been carried out within the HESSP project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 898052.

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